

FLOATECH

D2.4. Full report on the estimated reduction of uncertainty in comparison to the state-of-the-art codes OpenFAST and DeepLines Wind™

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FLOATECH
THE FUTURE OF FLOATING WIND TURBINES

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Background: about the FLOATECH project

The FLOATECH project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union's H2020 programme aiming to increase the technical maturity and the cost competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) energy. This is particularly important because, due to the limitations of available installation sites onshore, offshore wind is becoming crucial to ensure the further growth of the wind energy sector.

The project is implemented by a European consortium of 5 public research institutions with relevant skills in the field of offshore floating wind energy and 3 industrial partners, two of which have been involved in the most recent developments of floating wind systems.

The approach of FLOATECH can be broken down into three actions:

- The development, implementation and validation of a user-friendly and efficient design engineering tool (named QBlade-Ocean) performing simulations of floating offshore wind turbines with an unprecedented combination of aerodynamic and hydrodynamic fidelity. The advanced modelling theories will lead to a reduction of the uncertainties in the design process and an increase of turbine efficiency.
- The development of two innovative control techniques (i.e., Active Wave-based feed-forward Control and the Active Wake Mixing) for Floating Wind Turbines and floaters, combining wave prediction and anticipation of induced platform motions. This is expected to improve the performance of each machine and to minimize wake effects in floating wind farms, leading to a net increase in the annual energy production of the farm.
- The economic analysis of these concepts to demonstrate qualitatively and quantitatively the impact of the developed technologies on the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) of FOW technology.

In addition to the technological and economic impacts, the project is expected to have several impacts at societal, environmental and political levels, such as: public acceptance, due to no noise and visibility issues of FOWT; very low impact on biodiversity and wildlife habitat because no piles are needed to be installed into the seabed; the use of less material and space thanks to an environmentally friendly design; the promotion of the installation of FOW in transitional water depths (30-50 m), as the costs for FOW at those locations will become more competitive compared to the fixed bottom foundations.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
OF	OpenFAST
DL	DeepLines
QB	QBlade-Ocean
DOF	Degree of Freedom
TT Fx	Tower Top fore-aft force
TT Fy	Tower Top side-side force
TT Mx	Tower Top side-side moment
TT My	Tower Top fore-aft moment
TB Fx	Tower Base fore-aft force
TB Fy	Tower Base side-side force
TB Mx	Tower Base side-side moment
TB My	Tower Base fore-aft moment
BR Mxb	Blade root edgewise bending moment
BR Myb	Blade root flapwise bending moment
BR Mxc	Blade root in-plane bending moment
BR Myc	Blade root out-of-plane bending moment
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
DEL	Damage Equivalent Load
DLC	Design Load Case

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the FLOATECH project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007142.

In work package 2 (WP2) a detailed validation and verification of the capabilities of QBlade-Ocean is carried out. A detailed description of the models used in the validation is provided in Deliverable 2.1 [1] and results of the validation that was carried out are presented in Deliverable 2.2 [2]. Some modifications to the models used in Task 2.1 have been adopted in Task 2.2, as described in deliverable D2.3, in order to have more realistic results when full scale FOWT models are considered. This document is based on the work described in the previous deliverables and aims to report a comprehensive code-to-code comparison, thus supporting a quantification study of the uncertainty in the predicted FOWT behaviour. Starting from the data gathered in the database collected through deliverable D2.3, containing Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) calculations in various design load situations, computed with three different codes, a comprehensive comparison of simulation results is then reported. Three FOWT concepts are simulated in a variety of design load cases (DLCs), as explained in the D2.3 deliverable document.

The current document reports the results of the analysis procedure applied to the gathered simulation data, according to the following scheme:

- Presentation of significant aggregate data obtained through post-processing of the dataset described in [3]. In particular:
 - Global statistics (mean value, maximum and minimum value) of relevant motion and load related data;
 - Extreme loads calculated according to standardized procedure (IEC extreme loads as described in [4]);
 - Fatigue loads, represented by Damage Equivalent Loads (DELs) for acting on the main FOWT components;
- Comparison of the previously reported results between the three codes for each of the considered FOWT models;
- Discussion of the outcomes of the comparison, attempting to find, wherever possible, reasonable explanations for the differences between codes and quantification the uncertainty related to the use of state-of-the-art numerical codes for the prediction of FOWTs behaviour.

2 INTRODUCTION

QBlade-ocean is a FOWT simulation tool that was partly developed withing the FLOATECH H2020 project (www.floatech-project.org). The advanced wind turbine simulation tool Qblade was expanded in work package 1 to be able to model FOWTs [5,6] and validated in work package 2 [1,2]. The tool includes advanced physical models, such as a Lifting-Line Free Vortex Wake (LLFVW) module for the solution of unsteady aerodynamic loads and a non-linear multibody FEA module for the solution of structural dynamics. Hydrodynamic modelling is also state of the art: potential-flow or strip-theory based models can be modelled and advanced features such as wave stretching models and explicit buoyancy computations have been implemented. The scope of this work is twofold: firstly to show the level of uncertainty in load prediction that can be expected in a complex computation such as the simulation of a FOWT in complex environmental conditions. This is achieved by discussing the differences between the numerical models. Aligning the outputs of the three numerical codes involved in this comparison required significant amount of work and discrepancies are found to be dependent not only on model theory but also on model set-up and on output conventions and export. The second objective is to investigate the differences that can be expected in the prediction of FOWT dynamics and loads when using a higher-fidelity tool such as Qblade-Ocean with respect to other numerical models, and how they may be tied to the underlying physics.

In the next sections we will report the results of the postprocessing analysis of a simulation dataset generated in this work package for three Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) models using three different codes with different modelling assumptions.

A comparative survey of the models used in this study is presented in sec. 3, together with a brief description of the characteristics of the code. The FOWT models, already introduced in previous work package deliverables [1–3], are briefly described in section 4.

Section 5 describes the simulation settings, as defined in terms of the assumed meteorological and operating conditions, indicating the considered Design Load Cases (DLC). The selected simulation set has been defined according to a subset of the IEC standard design requirements, considering the environmental conditions of a European offshore site (west of Barra Isle).

In section 7, 8 and 9, a graphic representation of the comparison is presented, considering three different aspects: a comparison of global statistic data for the DLC 1.2 simulation subsets, a comparison of the maximum values of the some interesting response parameters, a comparison of the 1 Hz Damage Equivalent loads (DELs) representing the fatigue actions on main turbine components. The main discussion points are summarized in section 10 and 11.

3 CHARACTERISTICS AND ASSUMPTIONS OF THE COMPARED SOFTWARE CODES

A short overview of the codes used in the generation of the reference dataset, gathered in deliverable D2.3 [2], will be presented in the next subsections. Table 1 provides a summary of the modelling capabilities of the software packages.

Table 1: Overview of software tools (adapted from [2])

	QBlade-Ocean	OpenFAST	Deeplines Wind™
Open Source?	Yes	Yes	No
Graphical user interface?	Yes	No	Yes
Distribution	Free online	Free online	Commercial
Structural model: Blades (MB- Multibody)	MB, Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.	MB, Modal reduction, Geometrically exact beam theory	MB, Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.
Structural model: Tower	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.	Modal reduction.	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.
Structural model: Substructure	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams. (floating, fixed bottom)	Craig-Bampton method (fixed bottom).	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams. (floating, fixed bottom)
Aerodynamics: On-blade	Blade elements. Multi-polar. Dynamic stall: Øye, B-L, Gormont, ATE Flap. Tower model.	Blade elements. Dynamic stall: Øye, B-L, Boeing-Vertol. Tower model.	Blade elements. Dynamic stall: Øye, Risø, Boeing-Vertol. Tower model.
Aerodynamics: Rotor/wake	Unsteady BEM, Free-vortex wake, Vortex particle	BEM, Dynamic inflow. Free-vortex wake (OLAF)	Steady BEM, Dynamic Inflow.
Hydrodynamics	Full Morison approach, Lin. Potential flow. 2 nd Order QTF	Full Morison approach, Lin. Potential flow. 2 nd Order QTF	Full Morison approach, Lin. Potential flow. 2 nd Order QTF
Hydrostatics	Linear buoyancy, explicit buoyancy	Linear buoyancy, explicit buoyancy	Explicit buoyancy
Environmental: Wind field	Turbsim, Hub-height files.	Turbsim, Hub-height files.	Turbsim, Hub-height files.
Environmental: Wave field	Regular, Irregular (numerous spectra), Multidirectional, Imported	Regular, Irregular (numerous spectra), Multidirectional, Import as time series.	Regular, Irregular (numerous spectra), Multidirectional, Import as time series.
Controller formats	Bladed, TUB, DTU	Bladed	Bladed

3.1 QBLADE-OCEAN

QBlade-Ocean (hereafter QB) is a multi-physics code, covering the complete range of aspects required for the aero-servo-hydro-elastic simulation of horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines.

QB uses a Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake method (LLFVW) for aerodynamic calculations. In this method, the rotor wake is explicitly modelled through Lagrangian vortex elements. This results in a more accurate and detailed spatial and temporal representation of the rotor induction, when compared to Blade Element Momentum (BEM) approaches, and fully resolves the velocity distribution behind the rotor.

QB models the structural dynamics using a multi-body formulation. The components of the multi-body model can be either point masses or rigid- and/or flexible Euler-Bernoulli beam elements in a co-rotational formulation. The structural model uses a co-rotational beam element formulation implemented within the multi-physics solver Project CHRONO [7]. This allows for the treatment of highly nonlinear deflections of beam elements.

A full report of the additional development of QB done within the FLOATECH project can be found in [5]. The QB user training manual can be found in [6].

3.2 OPENFAST

OpenFAST (hereafter OF) is a state-of-the-art multi-physics code, developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) to model horizontal axis wind turbines. Like QB, the code is open-source and is able to model onshore and offshore wind turbines, both bottom-fixed and floating. All the calculations presented in this report are performed with OpenFAST v3.0.0.

The wind turbine's wake induction is modelled using blade-element-momentum theory (BEM), with corrections for high thrust, tip and root losses and misaligned inflow. Corrections for dynamic stall are used, in the form of the Beddoes-Leishman dynamic stall model. Dynamic wake effects are modelled using the approach proposed by Øye [8]. This model is able to account for the fact that changes in blade induction do not apply instantly to the entire wake by applying a filtering procedure to the axial and tangential induced velocities at each blade section.

The floating support substructures are modelled as 6-DOF rigid bodies. Their interaction with the sea is computed using HydroDyn [9], OF's hydrodynamics module. Similarly to QB, hydrodynamics can be modelled using potential flow theory, a Morison equation approach or a mix of the two. For test cases presented in this report, potential flow theory is used, with the addition of the Morison equation to model quadratic drag.

The structural dynamics are solved using the modal-based structural module ElastoDyn [10]. The structural deformations are calculated as linear superposition of the predetermined mode shapes, allowing for a very fast solution with limited degrees of freedom to solve for [11]. Moorings are modelled using MoorDyn [12], a dynamic lumped-mass mooring line model. The model accounts for internal axial stiffness and damping forces, weight and buoyancy forces, hydrodynamic forces from Morison's equation, and vertical spring-damper forces from contact with the seabed.

3.3 DEEPLINES

DeepLines™ (hereafter DL) is a commercial integrated software solution to perform in-place and installation analyses of various offshore structures, based on the finite element method. It allows for design of flexible risers, power cables and umbilical, pipelines, mooring systems, towed systems and simulations of marine operations. DL is part of the marine software solutions suite developed by Principia and IFP Energies Nouvelles. This numerical tool is based on the program Flexan, initially developed for flexible risers and used since 1980.

To address the needs for an overall design tool raised by the development of offshore wind turbines platforms, a new module DeepLines WIND (hereafter DL) was created in 2011. DL is designed to perform fully-coupled dynamic finite element analysis. It accounts for combined effects of aerodynamic loads on the blades, active pitch control, hydrodynamic loads on the floating platform and dynamic mooring loads. Several BEM models are implemented in an external .dll library to calculate the aerodynamic loads. DL is able to simulate both horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines. The aerodynamic model in DL uses a BEM approach coupled with a dynamic inflow model. In this case no unsteady blade aerodynamics model has been applied.

4 MODEL DEFINITIONS

A brief summary of the model configuration data, already presented in a previous deliverable [1–3], will be reported here for the sake of completeness. The main characteristics of each of the three tested models will be presented in the next subsections. Not all three codes, with the exception of QB, have been tested with all three test cases. A summary of the codes and their application for the different test cases is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of compared codes for each test case

Code Test case	DeepLines Wind (DL)	OpenFAST (OF)	QBlade-Ocean (QB)
NREL 5MW OC4		✓	✓
SOFTWIND 10MW	✓	✓	✓
HEXAFLOAT 10MW	✓		✓

4.1 SOFTWIND

This section describes the DTU 10MW RWT mounted on the SOFTWIND spar platform, henceforth called the 10MW SOFTWIND test case. The SOFTWIND platform is a spar-buoy platform originally developed and tested by Ecôle Centrale Nantes (ECN) [13] and was used in WP2.1 of the current project [1,2]. The wind turbine rotor is described in [14], while the semi-submersible and mooring line layout is described in [1,13]. The model used in the current study is derived from the definition that was used in WP2.1 [1,2], however some adaptations have been done so that it can be used in a full set of design load calculations. These modifications are described in [6] but will be briefly summarized here. The model that was used in WP2.1 featured platform mass and inertia distribution as close as possible to the experimental article described in [13]. In the experimental model, batteries and control electronics are housed inside the spar, altering the mass and inertia distribution. The model used in WP2.2 features a lower center of gravity to increase stability in severe seas, making the test case more representative of an actual floating platform. The tower properties have also been changed. In fact, stiffening of the tower was considered necessary to avoid a 3P excitation of the structure, as the natural frequencies of the tower used in WP2.1 are located in the 3P range for some wind speeds. Therefore, the tower originally developed by Olav-Olsen¹ for the OO-Star platform in the LifeS50+ Horizon 2020 project [15] is used in the current model. A schematic representation of the turbine mounted on the spar floater is shown in Figure 1.

¹ The OO-Star Wind Floater has been developed by Dr.Techn. Olav Olsen (OO) since 2010 and is the property of Floating Wind Solutions AS. OO has approved that the public model from Lifes50+ can be used for the research activities within FLOATECH. The model shall not be used for other purposes unless it is explicitly approved by OO.

Figure 1: SOFTWIND turbine model in QB.

4.1.1 Numerical model set-up

The numerical set-up choices for the SOFTWIND test case in the three numerical codes (DL, OF, QB) used in this work, mostly carry over from those presented in Deliverable 2.2 of the FLOATECH project [2]. The increase in tower mass and change in platform characteristics that was described in section 4.1 however required a re-tuning of the models.

Aerodynamics the set-up described in [2] is left unchanged for QB and DL. For OF however, the aerodynamic definition was updated and AeroDyn v15 [16] was used in place of the legacy AeroDyn v14. This allowed for improved accuracy in modelling the pre-bend of the blades. Moreover, a dynamic induction model can now be used in OF, allowing for this numerical model to empirically capture dynamic induction effects. The model developed by Øye is used [8], as described in [17]. The model introduces a time-lag in the calculated induction factors, empirically accounting for the “wake memory” effect. It depends on two time constants τ_1 and τ_1 . In the OF model these constants are left equal to their default values, computed based on rotor-averaged axial induction [17].

Turbine definition tower structural properties and floater mass and inertia properties were changed in accordance with section 4.1. For the DL model however, this resulted in large discrepancies in the response of the structure from a dynamic standpoint, with large differences in free-decay tests being noticed. To better align the DL model to OF and QB, the following was done:

1. A transverse drag coefficient (C_a) of 0.5 is applied to the spar structure through strip theory. As described in [2], a hybrid potential flow – strip theory approach was used in all three codes. In particular, Morrison’s equation is used to account for quadratic drag in the models, while radiation damping, added mass and linear excitation force are included through an externally computed potential flow solution. In the DL model however, to align the surge and sway free-decay natural frequencies, an added mass coefficient of 0.5 was added in the strip-theory solution, effectively counting added mass twice respect to OF and QB;
2. Roll and Pitch floater inertias are decreased approximately 40% to align the natural frequencies in roll and pitch;
3. As discussed in [2], mooring line lengths were tuned in each numerical models as a compromise between natural frequency in surge and mean mooring line tension. It is worth pointing out here that the compromise found for DL led to slightly longer lines and thus lower tensions than the tunings that were done for OF and QB.

Table 3: Masses, inertias and strip-theory transverse and axial coefficients for SOFTWIND model in the three numerical models

variable	OF	QB	DL	units
RNA mass	676804	676950	676755	kg
CoG RNA	116.67	-	118.42	m
Tower mass	1.2598E+6	1.2568 E+6	1.1969 E+6	kg
CoG Tower	41.03	38.31	49.814	m
Platform mass	1.9919E+7	1.9919E+7	1.9919E+7	kg
CoG Ptfm	-74.92	-74.92	-74.89	m
Ixx Ptfm	9.75E+9	9.75E+9	5.87E+9	kg*m ²
Iyy Ptfm	9.75E+9	9.75E+9	5.87E+9	kg*m ²
Izz Ptfm	9.3E+8	9.3E+8	9.31E+8	kg*m ²
FOWT mass	2.1855E+7	2.2792 E+7	2.1793 E+7	kg
CoG FOWT	-62.30	-61.91	-67.51	m
C_a axial	0	0	0	-
C_d axial	5	5	8	-
C_a trasv	0	0	0.5	-
C_d trasv	0.3	0.3	0.3	-

A summary of the masses, inertias and strip-theory coefficients that were applied to the SOFTWIND floater are summarized in Table 3.

4.2 NREL 5MW OC4

This section describes the NREL 5MW RWT mounted on the DeepCWind semi-submersible platform, henceforth called the 5MW OC4 test case. This wind turbine model was extensively used in the OC4 code-to-code comparison [18] and hence the model definition is publicly available [19]. The wind turbine rotor and tower are described in [20], while the semi-submersible and mooring line layout is described in [19].

Figure 2: Visualization of the 5MW OC4 FOWT model in QB in regular waves.

With respect to the OC5 model that was used in WP 2.1 [2] the floater geometry is unchanged, while the tower, nacelle and blades are those of the NREL 5MW RWT [20], as opposed to the model scale tower and blades used in OC5 [21]. The model defined within this study follows the definition in [19].

4.2.1 Numerical model set-up

The OC4 model is set-up with the same approach that was used for OC5: aerodynamics are modelled with BEM in OF and LLFVW in QB, structural dynamics are accounted for in OF with a modal approach and in QB with a multi-body FEM model, Linear Potential Morrison Drag (LPDM) approach is used for hydrodynamics in both codes, as well as a dynamic mooring cable model.

In OF, the public OC4 definition that is found on GitHub (https://github.com/OpenFAST/r-test/tree/main/glue-codes/openfast/5MW_OC4Semi_WSt_WavesWN) was used as model definition. Blade Element Momentum theory (BEM) augmented with a dynamic induction model proposed by Øye is used [8]. Blade-level unsteadiness is modelled using a Beddoes-Leishman type dynamic stall model. This aerodynamic model will be referred to as DBEM (Dynamic-BEM). In agreement with standard industrial practices, corrections for root and tip losses, non-uniform

non-aligned inflow and high induction are also included in the aerodynamic model. Details regarding the specific BEM implementation can be found in [22]. Flexible tower and blades are modelled using ElastoDyn using a modal formulation, where the blades and tower deformations are computed by superimposing pre-computed modal deformations.

Hydrodynamics are modelled using a combination of potential flow and strip theory that is used to compute quadratic drag. The drag coefficients computed with the approach described in [19] are used in both OF and QB. After comparing free-decay tests, lower linear damping was noted for OF respect to QB. However, given the excellent agreement that was noted in unsteady wave tests, it was preferred to not tune the models to improve linear damping agreement and instead maintain the definitions identical in the interest of the code-to-code comparison. For the potential flow solution, WAMIT-computed hydrodynamic coefficients provided during the OC4 projects have been used for first-order loads. Second-order potential-flow load quadratic transfer functions (QTFs) are computed using NEMOH, which was recently extended to be able to compute QTFs within work package 1 of the FLOATECH project (<https://gitlab.com/lheea/Nemoh>). This has allowed us to model second order loads for the range of wave headings (-150 to 150°) that are used in this project (section 5). With respect to hydrodynamics, QB features two main improvements over the current OF version; firstly, the hydrostatic buoyancy force is discretely calculated based on the displaced volume by the floating structure. We refer to this approach as explicit buoyancy. To avoid a double-accounting of the buoyancy forces through the potential flow excitation force and this explicit buoyancy approach, instead of evaluating buoyancy for the instantaneous sea level we calculate the buoyancy with respect to the mean sea level (MSL). In contrast buoyancy is modelled in OF as a constant force and a linear stiffness to account for deviations from the equilibrium. Secondly, Wheeler kinematic stretching method is applied in QB to approximate the water kinematics above MSL. Further details can be found in [2].

4.3 DTU 10MW HEXAFLOAT

The DTU 10MW Hexafloat model description can be found in Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2 of the FLOATECH project [1,2]. The substructure of the Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT is developed by Saipem® and is a two-part floater depicted in Figure 3. It consists of a floating hexagonal structure and a counterweight linked together with six tendons. No changes have been made to the Hexafloat model with respect to the definition shown in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2].

Figure 3: The Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT aero-hydro-elastic model in QB.

5 CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SIMULATION DATASET

The objective of the current exercise is to perform a code-to-code comparison in realistic environmental conditions. To achieve this objective, three preliminary actions are necessary, and are illustrated in this section:

- i. Definition of a series of combination of operating conditions and environmental conditions (Design Load Cases – DLCs) that are relevant for extreme and fatigue loading on FOWTs
- ii. Definition of long-term environmental conditions to use in the DLCs defined in i)
- iii. Definition of a procedure to match wind and wave inputs amongst the compared codes to ensure that Time series can be compared, in addition to more commonly presented statistical comparisons

All three actions are illustrated in this section. In particular, the first action is explained in section 5.1, while section 5.2 explains the procedure followed to compute a long-term environmental representation of an offshore site of choice. Finally, the procedure to ensure environmental inputs match in QB, OF and DL is explained in section 5.3. The reference systems that are used

in this analysis are indicated in section 5.4. The analysed datasets are public, and their public location is specified in section 5.5

5.1 SIMULATED DESIGN LOAD CASES (DLC)

The DLCs that make up the current database have been selected in order to provide a good estimation of fatigue and extreme loads whilst limiting as much as possible the total number of simulations. In fact, considering the full design space is not needed since full turbine certification is out of the scope of this project, while it was important to include those functioning conditions that could make differences between the modeling approaches more evident. The list of selected DLCs does not include cases where fault events are simulated. This simplifies future comparisons using this dataset.

The final list contains the same DLCs that were simulated in the design of the IEA 15MW RWT [23,24], with the addition of DLC 1.2 for fatigue loads. Except for fault cases, which are not included in the current list, they match the load cases simulated by Jonkman in [25]. In the latter reference, the authors state that these DLCs are selected to cover essential design-driving situations, which is the same objective of the current document. An overview of the DLCs that were simulated is shown in Table 4.

5.1.1 Turbulent wind

The number of used turbulent wind-wave seeds was partially limited. In fact, when conducting an extensive comparison such as the one in this study memory requirements to store the full-field wind fields that are needed for the coupled simulations can become relevant. Therefore, the following approach is adopted:

- In DLC 1.2, simulations with 0° and $+10^\circ$ yaw misalignment share the same wind field. This DLC is used for fatigue load calculations and therefore is less sensitive to seed-dependent transient events.
- In DLC 6.1 and 6.3, two simulations per wind/wave misalignment and yaw error will be performed. Therefore, a total of two wind fields will be generated. Simulations are differentiated by yaw angle.

The total number of wind fields required for the full DLC calculation is shown in table 4. As explained in section 5.3, significant effort was put in to ensure that the environmental inputs match as much as possible in the compared codes, thus lowering the number of required seeds to have a good statistical comparison.

Table 4: DLCs in code-to-code comparison

DLC	Wind Speed [m/s]	Sea Condition	Significant Wave Height [m]	Peak Period [s]	Wave Heading [°]	Sea Currents Condition	Total N° sims
1.2	5-25	NSS	1-9	8-14	-150°-150°	None	504
1.3	5	NSS	1.589253	9.788171	0	None	9
	7		1.79685	9.992163	0		9
	9		2.066758	10.24619	0		9
	11		2.396227	10.54261	0		9
	13		2.78555	10.87777	0		9
	15		3.237992	11.25141	0		9
	17		3.757419	11.66434	0		9
	19		4.346084	12.1166	0		9
	21		5.004369	12.60752	0		9
	23		5.731637	13.1363	0		9
	25		6.52699	13.70255	0		9
1.4	9.5	NSS	2.066758	10.24619	0	None	2
	11.5		2.396227	10.54261	0		2
	13.5		2.78555	10.87777	0		2
1.6	5	SSS	8.472305	15.05372	0	None	9
	7		9.182249	15.53933	0		9
	9		9.698228	15.89071	0		9
	11		9.970977	16.07605	0		9
	13		10.05924	16.13597	0		9
	15		10.12899	16.1833	0		9
	17		10.35074	16.33371	0		9
	19		10.80451	16.64112	0		9
	21		11.48977	17.10469	0		9
	23		12.35813	17.69156	0		9
	25		13.34401	18.35793	0		9
6.1	36.92	ESS	16.42	18.68	-30°/0°/30°	None	18
6.3	31.9	ESS	11.93	15.95	-30°/0°/30°	None	18
6.2	36.92	ESS	16.42	18.68	45°/90°/135°/180°	None	12

A schematic representation of the wind field box that is used in the simulations is shown in Figure 4. The same wind fields are shared by the three test cases, whether they use the NREL 5MW or the DTU 10MW rotor. Mean wind speed is imposed at 100 m above mean sea water level (MSWL), in consistency with the ERA5 hindcast database. Because of wind shear, wind speed will be slightly lower than the imposed value at 100m for the OC4 test case and slightly higher for SOFTWIND and HEXAFLOAT test cases, as if these test machines were installed at

the selected location (section 5.2). Turbulent wind fields are generated using TurbSim v2.0.0 [26,27], with IEC-Kaimal spectral model and spectral coherence model.

Table 5: number of wind seeds required for DLC calculation.

DLC	seeds per ws	n° ws	tot sims
1.3	9	11	99
1.2	252		
1.6	9	11	99
6.1	2	1	2
6.2	2	1	2
6.3	2	1	2
TOTAL			454

Figure 4: schematic view of wind field box (black), DTU 10MW rotor (red) and NREL 5MW rotor (black).

5.1.2 Wind shear

Wind shear is modelled using a power law. In normal conditions, a shear exponent of 0.14 is used, as specified in IEC 61400-1 [4]. This exponent applies to all simulations with Normal Turbulence Model (NTM) and Extreme Turbulence Model (ETM). In extreme conditions, a shear exponent of 0.12 is used, as specified in the LifeS50+ design basis [26]. The latter exponent applies to simulations with the Extreme Wind Model (EWM).

5.2 ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

Calculations in the current dataset are performed for an offshore installation site west of the island of Barra (Scotland).

The West of Barra site is located on the European continental shelf and therefore, water depths are limited to about 120-130 m. According to [27], average depth at the site is 95 m and within the identified installation area depth varies between 56 and 118 m. Water depth in the point where met-ocean conditions were sampled for the FLOATECH project is 123 m according to [28]. Importantly for WP2, this depth allows for the sampling of mid-depth wave characteristics, representative of sites where FOWT wind parks are planned to be installed. As a matter of fact, if we look at the only two operating commercial FOWT wind farms in Europe at the current date, the Hywind Scotland [29] and WindFloat ATLANTIC [30] wind farms, reported water depth is 90 and 100 m [29,30] respectively. For the generation of the current dataset, water depth is ignored, and the West of Barra site is used only to extract wave and wind characteristics. The considered water depth is defined based on the nominal installation depth of the three test cases that were considered: 200 m for the NREL 5MW OC4 and DTU 10MW SOFTWIND models and 250 m for the DTU 10MW HEXAFLOAT model. Moreover, no currents are considered in the calculations. A water density of 1025 kg/m³ is assumed.

5.2.1 Environmental condition database

The combination of wind speed, significant wave height and wind-wave misalignment (this latter point being a distinctive feature of the analysis, since it is not always accounted for) are defined on a Design Load Case basis with the procedure described in [31]. Starting from hindcast wind and wave data for the West of Barra site, a joint probabilistic model of the four environmental variables (wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period, wind-wave misalignment) is derived. The model is then used to compute environmental contours that define the extreme met-ocean conditions (DLC 1.6, 6.1, 6.2, 6.3). The expected or normal met-ocean conditions are instead used in DLCs 1.2 and 1.3.

The complete dataset is openly available at the following link:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6972014>

5.3 CALCULATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL INPUTS

Once the DLCs are defined (section 5.1) and the long-term representation of the installation site has been computed (section 5.2), turbulent wind fields and irregular wave fields for each simulation must be defined. To ensure that Time series can be compared, providing insight on

how the different models in the compared codes are able to reproduce physics that lead to, for instance, extreme component loads, care has been put into ensuring that QB, OF and DL share the same inputs.

Therefore, identical turbulent wind boxes are generated using the same version of TurbSim and imported in the three codes. This resulted in identical wind fields for QB and OF. For DL a time-shift is noted. This is partially due to the fact that DL exports wind speed at the RNA, while OF and QB export wind speed at the (0,0,HubHeight) position. Therefore, when the FOWT moves, a shift in the output will be present. However, this does not completely explain the time-shift. The observed time shift also depends on how the turbulent wind boxes are imported into the three codes and DL seems to differ from OF and QB in this regard. This implies that the time-series in DL are not always punctually comparable to those coming from OF and QB.

Wave Time series were generated in DL and then imported in QB and OF, where they are decomposed into their frequency components using FFT. Thus, wave fields are identical in the three codes.

5.4 REFERENCE SYSTEMS AND OUTPUTS

A complete list of the available outputs can be found in Deliverable D2.3, amongst which this work builds upon. The main sensors that are compared herein include blade root loads in blade reference system, shaft loads, yaw-bearing loads, tower base loads and mooring line tensions. A brief description of the reference systems in which the outputs are expressed is provided here:

- **Tower bottom reference system (t):** ref. system moves with tower base. If no platform displacement, x-axis directed downwind and z-axis directed upward. Y-axis normal to x and z axis.
- **Tower-top reference system (p):** same as tower base reference system but deforms with tower top
- **Coned reference system (c):** z-axis directed along blade pitch axis. Y-axis parallel to blade chord is blade pitch and twist are zero. X-axis normal to z and y axes.
- **Blade reference system (b):** same as coned reference system but pitches with blade. In DL loads in the "b" reference system do not pitch with the blades.
- **Shaft reference system (s):** x-axis directed along rotor shaft. Z-axis directed upwards (normal to x-axis). Y-axis normal to x and z-axis.

5.5 DATA AVAILABILITY

The complete dataset is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254241>

Some simulations in OF and DL experienced crashes and could not be completed within the timeframe of the work package. The crashes are noted only for a limited number of cases. The fact that the dataset is incomplete for OF and DL in some cases, however, may skew extreme and fatigue loads in comparison with the other codes. An overview of the status of the complete/incomplete simulations is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Status of datasets for each code

code	DLC	status	notes
OC4			
OF	1.2	504/504	
	1.3	99/99	
	1.4	06/06	
	1.6	99/99	
	6.1	18/18	
	6.2	16/16	
	6.3	18/18	
QB	1.2	504/504	
	1.3	99/99	
	1.4	06/06	
	1.6	99/99	
	6.1	18/18	
	6.2	16/16	
	6.3	18/18	
SOFTWIND			
OF	1.2	504/504	
	1.3	99/99	
	1.4	06/06	
	1.6	99/99	
	6.1	18/18	
	6.2	8/16	Missing Seeds: 10003 (mis 30 yaw 45), 10003 (mis 30 yaw 90), 10003 (mis -30 yaw 45), 10003 (mis -30 yaw 90).
	6.3	18/18	
QB	1.2	504/504	
	1.3	99/99	
	1.4	06/06	
	1.6	99/99	
	6.1	18/18	
	6.2	16/16	
	6.3	18/18	
DL	1.2	498/504	Missing Seeds: 8 (y10), 11 (y0 & y10), 14 (y10), 15 (y10), 14 (y0)

	1.3	86/99	Missing Seeds: 663, 664, 665, 672, 673, 674, 681, 682, 683, 690, 691, 692, 698.
	1.4	06/06	
	1.6	99/99	
	6.1	12/18	Missing Seeds: all (yaw -10)
	6.2	12/16	Missing Seeds: all (yaw 45)
	6.3	12/18	Missing Seeds: all (yaw -20)
HEXAFLOAT			
QB	1.2	504/504	
	1.3	99/99	
	1.4	06/06	
	1.6	99/99	
	6.1	18/18	
	6.2	16/16	
	6.3	18/18	
DL	1.2	487/504	Missing Seeds: 218 (y0), 221 (y0), 222 (y0 & y10), 227 (y10), 230 (y0 & y10), 232 (y0 & y10), 234 (y10), 237 (y0 & y10), 238 (y0 & y10), 239 (y0), 241 (y0 & y10)
	1.3	99/99	
	1.4	06/06	
	1.6	99/99	
	6.1	18/18	Missing Seeds: all (yaw -10).
	6.2	16/16	Missing Seeds: all (yaw 45).
	6.3	18/18	Missing Seeds: all (yaw -20).

6 COMPUTATIONAL TIME

The main scope of this document is the comparison of the performance of FOWT simulation codes in terms of the physics that they are able to solve. However, for a more complete picture of the capabilities of the compared softwares, some information regarding computational requirements will be given herein. It must be noted that this information is valid strictly for the test cases and set-ups that they are relative to and generally valid.

For a DLC 1.2 simulation of the SOFTWIND testcase, that is simulated with all three codes (4000 s of simulated time):

- Qblade-Ocean is run on a desktop workstation equipped with a 12th Gen Intel® Core™ i7-12700KF processor and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3070 Ti graphics card. 20 simulations are run in parallel and average wall clock time per simulation is approximately 10400 s.
- OpenFAST is run on a desktop workstation equipped with a i9 10th Gen Core™ processor. 12 simulations are run in parallel and average wall clock time per simulation is approximately 1140 s.

- DeepLines Wind™ is run on a cloud computing service with Intel Xeon Processors (Skylake), @ 2.4 Ghz. 34 simulations are run on a 36-core server, or 16 simulations are run on a 14-core server. Average wall clock time is 24900 s per simulation. Standard hard-drives are used for storage. This is relevant as I/O time is often significant, and calculations will run faster if SSDs are used.

The wake is solved with a medium-fidelity LLFVW model in QB as opposed to a low-fidelity DBEM model that is used in OF and DL. Such a wake model requires GPU acceleration to be run efficiently, hence the GPU in the QB workstation is mentioned. SOFTWIND simulations did not include second order wave loads. The use of Quadratic Transfer Functions (QTFs) can add significant computational time to QB simulations. QB runs were performed using QBlade Enterprise Edition (EE) that allows for multiple simulations to be run in parallel, a feature that is not available in the open-source Community Edition (CE). In comparison to the other codes, OF requires much less computational time to run. It must be noted however that this code was run with lower fidelity modal based structural dynamics model and lower fidelity dynamic-BEM aerodynamics.

7 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF NORMAL OPERATING CONDITIONS

The simulation datasets, previously generated, undergo the following procedure to determine a set of significant statistic parameters:

- A subset of the database comprising only the results of DLC 1.2 (related to normal operation in normal turbulent wind and normal sea state conditions) is considered. The choice of this subset is motivated by the fact that this subset is the largest among the considered DLC, thus providing a statistically significant set of results with homogeneous environmental conditions;
- The simulations in the data set are processed using a wide-spread tool developed by NREL for DLC postprocessing named MLife [32], mainly intended to fatigue analyses, but also able to generate statistics. The output of this processing phase is represented by a set of fundamental statistical data (mean, standard deviation, maximum, minimum) for each simulated condition defined by average wind speed and sea state (corresponding to single simulation file);
- A post-processing script is used to report the calculated statistics grouping the data based on wind speed. The grouped data are reported using a boxplot style in order to give a more concise representation of the large dataset. Simulation results are binned according to wind speed with a speed interval of 2 m/s, between 5 m/s and 25 m/s, thus

considering the following bins: $(4, 6] < (6, 8] < (8, 10] < (10, 12] \dots (18, 20] < (20, 22] < (22, 24] < (24, 26]$. For each bin, the box centre represents the mean value of the binned data, the boxplot height represents twice the mean standard deviation, while the whiskers represent the maximum and minimum value in the bin.

The data considered for the statistical comparison are collected in several groups, based on their meaning. Table 7 summarizes the analysed quantities.

Table 7. Variable considered for statistical analysis.

Data group	Variable considered for statistical analysis
Tower base loads	Tower base longitudinal (fore-aft) force, $TB F_x$ Tower base lateral (side-side) force, $TB F_y$ Tower base longitudinal (fore-aft) moment, $TB M_y$ Tower base lateral (side-side) moment, $TB M_x$
Tower top loads	Tower top longitudinal (fore-aft) force, $TT F_x$ Tower top lateral (side-side) force, $TT F_y$ Tower top longitudinal (fore-aft) moment, $TT M_y$ Tower top lateral (side-side) moment, $TT M_x$
Control related data	Generator Power Generator Torque Rotor speed Blade pitch angle
Platform motion data	Platform surge displacement Platform sway displacement Platform heave displacement Platform roll displacement Platform pitch displacement Platform yaw displacement
Rotor aerodynamics data	Aerodynamic thrust Aerodynamic torque
Blade data	Blade tip out-of-plane (OoP) deflection Blade tip in-plane (IP) deflection Blade root edgewise moment in blade pitching ref. system Blade root flapwise moment in blade pitching ref. system
Mooring data	Fairlead tension on the mooring lines <i>Fairlead tensions for OC4 and SOFTWIND (3 mooring lines)</i> <i>Tendon tensions for HEXAFLOAT (6 lines)</i>
Hydrodynamic data	Hydrostatic force Horizontal 1 st order hydrodynamic force Horizontal 2 nd order hydrodynamic force (<i>reported for OC4</i>)

7.1 SOFTWIND MODEL STATISTIC COMPARISON

The following figures report a comparison of the main aggregate statistical parameters, as previously defined, for the SOFTWIND model.

Platform motion statistics are shown in Figure 5. Focusing on fore-aft sensors such as platform surge and pitch, which are the ones most influenced by aerodynamic loads in addition to wave loads, similar overall trends can be noted. However, both OF and DL show larger means, standard deviations and maximum values than QB. Similar considerations are valid for the Yaw Degree of Freedom (DOF). Regarding side-side motion on the other hand, all three codes are very similar. Platform heave shows the most differences, mostly in mean value. These differences are attributed to different model tuning and carry over from the previous work conducted within this work package, and discussed in Deliverable D2.2 [2].

Figure 5: SOFTWIND aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Platform motion data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Global performance and control sensors are compared in Figure 6. Overall, the three codes behave well, but as was the case for fore-aft platform motion, larger standard deviation can be seen for OF and DL than for QB in generator power, generator torque and rotor speed. Differences in mean blade pitch can be seen in Figure 6. These are likely due to small differences in steady-state aerodynamic forces for the models, as discussed in D2.2 [2].

Figure 6: SOFTWIND aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Control related data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 7: SOFTWIND aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Tower base loads. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Tower top and tower base load statistics are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, respectively. The signature of rotor torque can clearly be seen in the tower top side-side bending moment (Mx) but it is negligible in the tower base side-side moment.

Figure 8: SOFTWIND aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Tower top loads. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 9: SOFTWIND aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Rotor aerodynamics data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 10: SOFTWIND aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Blade data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Statistics of the fairlead tensions, measured at the delta-connection, is shown in Figure 11. Fairleads 2 and 3 are directed upwind, 120° apart, while fairlead 1 is directed downwind, parallel to wind heading. As shown from the whiskers in Figure 11, the mooring lines never go slack during normal operation.

Figure 11: SOFTWIND aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Mooring line tensions. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Moreover, tensions are consistent for OF and QB, but an offset of approximately 10% in mean value is noted for DL. This difference is attributed to the different tuning of this model that was done during set-up.

7.2 OC4 MODEL STATISTIC COMPARISON

A comparison of the chosen set of aggregate statistics is reported for the OC4 model. The following figures report a comparison of the main statistical parameters, as previously defined, for the SOFTWIND model.

Mean platform motion statistics are shown in Figure 12. Good agreement between QB and OF in mean values can be noted. However, slightly greater standard deviations and peak loads can be noted for OF.

Figure 12: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Platform motion data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Control sensors are compared in Figure 13. Greater mean generator power, torque and rotor speed can be noted below rated wind speed for QB. On the other hand, mean blade pitch is higher above-rated wind speed for OF. Both factors indicate slight differences in mean aerodynamic loads between the two codes. In particular, the LLFVW module inside QB appears to predict greater torque than the DBEM algorithm in OF, an observation that was also noted in [33].

Figure 13: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Control related data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Tower top loads can be seen in Figure 15. As for the SOFTWIND test case, the influence of rotor torque on TT Mx can be clearly seen in Figure 15. Significantly larger maximum values of this metric can be seen for OF. The reason that leads to this difference is worth explaining, as it depends on complex interactions between aerodynamics, structural dynamics, control and hydrodynamics. In Figure 14 time series in proximity of the minimum value of TT Mx recorded in OF in DLC 1.2 at 17 m/s mean wind speed (Figure 14 (a-f)) and the time series in proximity of the maximum value of TT Mx recorded in OF in DLC 1.2 at 19 m/s mean wind speed (Figure 14 (a-f)) are shown. In both cases, the link between generator torque and TT Mx is apparent, as the instantaneous values of these two sensors are quite similar. When both the minimum and maximum values for OF are recorded, an abrupt change in generator torque can be noted. In fact, as rotor speed decreases, the generator abruptly transitions from above-rated to below-rated torque. For the OC4 test case, an aggressive minimum pitch saturation schedule is imposed in the ROSCO controller. The same settings as in the public example that can be found in the ROSCO repository (https://github.com/NREL/ROSCO/blob/main/Test_Cases/NREL-5MW/DISCON.IN) are used. Minimum pitch saturation consists in imposing a minimum blade

pitch angle as a function of the measured wind speed. It is used to perform peak shaving [34] and/or to prevent excessive reductions in blade pitch in response to fluctuations in wind speed due to turbulence, to lower aerodynamic peak loads. Once the minimum pitch angle as a function of the 1-second low-pass filtered velocity is reached, the generator transitions to below-rated operation to maintain rotor speed at it's rated value. The cause of rotor speed decrease can be traced back to decreasing aerodynamic torque, as wind speed decreases because of turbulence and platform pitch increases due to the instantaneous wave field, lowering relative velocity on the rotor even further. Because of the difference in blade pitch between QB and OF (as shown in Figure 13), pitch saturation is reached earlier by QB, that transitions to below-rated torque earlier than OF.

Figure 14: Time series near minimum TT My (left, DLC 1.2 seed 193, mean wind speed 17 m/s) and maximum TT Mx (right, DLC 1.2 seed 223, mean wind speed 19 m/s) during normal operation (DLC 1.2). (top to bottom) platform pitch, nacelle fore-aft velocity, blade pitch, generator torque, wind X velocity.

Moreover, once the transition occurs for OF, a relatively large oscillation at the first side-side tower natural frequency can be noted. On the other hand, the step change in generator torque does not initiate such an oscillation in QB, which in turn predicts lower peak TT Mx. Although damping ratios were not compared when the numerical models were set-up, 1% of critical damping ratio is specified in OF, while a Rayleigh damping coefficient of 0.00127 is specified in QB, leading to similar damping ratios at the tower natural frequency. In the other test-cases where a less aggressive minimum pitch saturation schedule is imposed, such a phenomenon is not noted.

Overall good statistical agreement is noted for tower base loads in Figure 16, indicating that both codes capture similar physics, however slightly greater peak loads for OF can be noted once again. Rotor-level aerodynamic loads are shown in Figure 17. While rotor torque is comparable, aerodynamic thrust is slightly higher for QB.

Figure 15: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Tower top loads. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Finally, mooring line loads are shown in Figure 19 and hydrodynamic forces in the surge DOF are shown in Figure 20. The mooring line configuration for this test case feature three lines 120° apart, with line two being directed directly upwind and the other two downwind. Although the two codes, once again, agree well, higher mean tensions in the downwind lines can be seen for OF. This is in-line with the lower mean surge that was noted in Figure 12.

As for hydrodynamic loads in Figure 20, sound agreement can be noted in 1st order surge force and hydrostatic force in heave. Very good agreement in second-order forces in surge can also be seen.

Figure 16: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Tower base loads. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 17: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Rotor aerodynamics data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 18: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Blade data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 19: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Mooring line tensions. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 20: OC4 aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Hydrodynamic loads. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

7.3 HEXAFLOAT MODEL STATISTIC COMPARISON

A comparison of the chosen set of aggregate statistics is reported for the 10MW Hexafloat model. The following figures show a statistical comparison of the main parameters, as previously defined, for the SOFTWIND and OC4 models. As discussed in section 4, for this case only results from the codes QB and DL are available.

Statistics of platform displacements are shown in Figure 21. The differences with respect to the previous 10MW SOFTWIND and 5MW OC4 models (sections 7.1 and 7.2) is apparent in the platform surge DOF, that shows peaks around rated wind speed in excess of 100m, much greater than the approximately 25m for the SOFTWIND platform and 12m for the OC4 platform. The platform offset is mainly driven by the design of the mooring system which is a “light” catenary design for the in 10MW Hexafloat model and is not attributable to the floater itself.

The variation in mean heave as a function of wind speed is also something that the other two test cases did not exhibit. This is linked to the platform surge offset: higher surge displacement leads to more tension in the mooring lines and a lower mean heave position. Although slightly higher mean surge can be noted for DL in above-rated wind speed, overall the two codes appear to be in very good agreement.

Figure 21: HEXAFLOAT aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Platform motion data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 22: HEXAFLOAT aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Aerodynamic thrust along low-speed shaft for QB and projected in wind heading direction for DL. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Performance and control sensor statistics in DLC 1.2 are shown in Figure 23. Mean power appears to be slightly higher for QB, as can be seen in the generator power statistics for below-rated operation and in the blade pitch statistics for above-rated operation. Moreover, higher variations in blade pitch and in rotor speed at high wind speeds can be seen for DL.

Figure 23: HEXAFLOAT aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Control related data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Tower top and tower base loads are shown in Figure 25 and Figure 24 respectively. Regarding tower-top loads, large differences can be seen in bending moments. In particular, side-side bending moment (M_x) is in good agreement between the two codes for mean values (driven by rotor torque, as discussed previously), but large differences in maximum/minimum values can be seen. For fore-aft tower top bending moment (M_x) no agreement in standard deviations or extremes can be seen. The reasons for this discrepancy are currently unknown and are being investigated.

Figure 24: HEXAFLOAT aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Tower base loads. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 25: HEXAFLOAT aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Tower top loads. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 26: HEXAFLOAT aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Blade data. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

Figure 27: HEXAFLOAT aggregate statistics in DLC 1.2 grouped by wind speed. Tendon tensions. Mean (black horizontal dash), standard deviation (box edges), min-max range (whiskers).

8 EXTREME LOADS

8.1 METHODS AND TOOLS

Wind turbine components need to be designed to withstand extreme loads predicted in numerical tools such as the ones compared in this study. Therefore, accurate estimation of extreme loads is essential for a cost-effective and safe wind turbine design. For this reason, the design codes benchmarked in this study are compared also on an extreme load basis.

Table 8. Variable considered for extreme load analysis.

Group	Variable
Platform motion data	Platform surge displacement Platform sway displacement Platform heave displacement Platform roll displacement Platform pitch displacement Platform yaw displacement
Blade 1 Tip deflections	Blade tip out-of-plane deflection (B1 Tip DX) Blade tip in-plane deflection (B1 Tip DY)
Shaft actions	Rotor thrust Shaft transvers force
Generator data	Generator Power $GenPwr$ Generator Torque $GenTq$
Aerodynamic data	Aero Thrust Aero Torque
Tower top loads	Tower top fore-aft force $TT Fx$ Tower top side-side force $TT Fy$
Tower base loads	Tower base fore-aft force $TB Fx$ Tower base side-side force $TB Fy$
Mooring lines	Mooring line tension (SOFTWIND & OC4) Tendon Tension (HEXAFLOAT)

Extreme loads were calculated using MExtremes [35], an NREL tool for the extraction of peak loads according to IEC 61400-1 indications. Maximum values are estimated for all the considered variables, for each wind speed bin from 5 to 25 m/s, according to the following procedure:

- The peak value from each file, corresponding to a given set of operating and environmental conditions is determined;
- For each DLC simulations are binned based on their mean wind speed;

- Two set of extreme values are then determined:
 - the absolute maximum among all the values in all of the bins (the diamonds in the following figures);
 - the value closest to but greater than the mean of the maximums in each bin, calculated in accordance to the definition in the MExtremes manual [35] (the bars in the following figures).

The latter method is similar to the indications in IEC 61400-1, Annex I [4], and is intended to remove any outliers in the extreme values. Data is collected in groups based on the location of the considered load-sensors, as described in Table 8.

For each test case, blade root edgewise and flapwise bending moments and tower base fore-aft and side-side bending moments are analyzed in detail, as they provide a good summary of the loading on the rotor and on the entire structure. Other key metrics are presented briefly. Further comments and observations for all three test cases are reported in section 10.

8.2 SOFTWIND MODEL EXTREME VALUE ANALYSIS

A comparison between the data described in the previous section is reported for the SOFTWIND model. As explained in detail in section 4 (Table 2), for this test case a three-way comparison between OF, DL and QB is performed. For each examined sensor the extreme values recorded for each of the numerical models is reported. The value closest to the mean of maximums, calculated in accordance to the definition in the MLife theory guide [32] is reported in the bars, while the absolute extreme without averaging is shown in the diamonds. In depth analysis of the time-series for some key load sensors is provided to give more insight into the physics leading to the extreme events.

Figure 28: SOFTWIND spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Platform motion data, maxima.

In Figure 28, the maximum platform displacements are shown. For these metrics, similar trends are noted for the compared numerical codes, although better agreement between OF and QB is shown. This could in part be due to the different modelling choices for the DL model, as discussed in section 4.1.1. Moreover, maximum displacements are located in the same DLC for OF and QB. Flapwise (My) and edgewise (Mx) blade root bending moment aggregated maximum values are shown in Figure 29. Flapwise maximum root bending moment is located in DLC 1.6 for all three codes. This metric is slightly higher for OF than it is for QB, while DL is approximately 10% lower than QB. For all three codes maximum values are similar for all three blades, suggesting that good statistical convergence of the maximum loads was reached. As for edgewise root bending moment (BR Mx), DL and QB predict the maximum to be located in a mix of DLC 1.3, 1.4 and 1.6, indicating that all three DLCs are similar in this load sensor. On the other hand, maximum edgewise root bending moment is in DLC 6.3 for all three blades for OF. A large difference between the mean of max and the non-averaged extreme load can be seen. As shown in the following, this is caused by a resonance.

Figure 29: SOFTWIND spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (top) Blade root moment data in blade ref. system, maxima. (bottom) Blade root moment data in blade non-pitching ref. system, maxima.

Time-series in correspondence of peak blade root flapwise loads are shown for OF and QB in Figure 30. In Figures (a-f) the recorded maximum QB load is recorded, in figures (g-l) maximum OF load is recorded. For both time instants, in addition to the Time series of TB My, Time series of other sensors are shown; platform pitch to give an indication of gravitational loading on the structure, RNA fore-aft acceleration for an indication of inertial loads on the structure, blade pitch and rotor speed to gauge the operating conditions of the machine, aerodynamic thrust for an indication of aerodynamic loading on the rotor. Finally, wave height and wind speed at hub height are also reported. For this test case, the peaks are located in DLC 1.6 for all three codes. In both the time-instants analysed in Figure 30, peak loading occurs in correspondence of a severe wave-train (Figure 30 (c, i)). By comparing Figure 30 (a-g) and (e-k), good correlation between rotor thrust and flapwise bending moment can be noted. This is not surprising as flapwise loads are typically driven by aerodynamic loading. Gravitational and inertial loads appear to be less influential for blade loads, confirming the trends that were noted in [36]. In fact, modern multi-MW wind turbine blades are relatively lightweight with respect to the other structural components such as the nacelle and tower. Therefore, although the gravitational and inertial loads driven by structural motion play a role, they are not as significant as those acting on the tower. Nonetheless, the platform motion contributes to the unsteady loading on the rotor, as fore-aft platform motion introduces variations in the apparent wind speed. As shown in Figure 30 (b) and (d) rotor speed correlates well with the pitch motion, which in turn drives blade pitch variations. Comparing QB and OF in Figure 30 (d), both rotor speed and blade pitch are very similar. Rotor thrust and torque in Figure 30 (d) show how, once again, QB and OF are very similar.

In both seeds shown in Figure 30, rotor thrust goes from a positive peak to a negative one between 3000 and 3100s, as a consequence of platform motion and blade pitch that rapidly rises from feather to more than 20° . Even in such dynamic inflow conditions, the DBEM wake model in OF is very close to the LLFVW model in QB in the prediction of global rotor aerodynamic loads (thrust and torque) as well as blade root bending moments. As for DL, platform dynamics (platform pitch and nacelle fore-aft acceleration) appear to be well predicted around the peak wave event that occurs around 3000 s, however differences with respect to QB and OF can be seen in the control signals and in the blade root flapwise bending moment. Such differences may be driven by the difference in instantaneous wind speed shown in Figure 30 (f)

Figure 30: Peak flapwise root bending moment (My) for QB (left, DLC1.6 seed 1039) and OF (right, DLC1.6 seed 1042). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust and torque (right axis, dashed line), (f) wind speed. $Max(My)$ is also in DLC1.6, seed 1039 for DL, but at different timestep.

Blade root edgewise extreme load Time series for QB and OF are shown in Figure 31. For QB and DL (not shown for brevity), maximum edgewise load is located in DLC1.4, and, as expected, is located in correspondence of the Extreme Operating Gust with Direction Change (ECD) event. In correspondence with the transient event, due to the combination of high wind speed and yaw angle, the turbine shuts down. The shut-down procedure is simulated by imposing a pitch-to-feather manoeuvre starting at 506 s with a 10 °/s pitch rate. In DL, although the pitching manoeuvre starts at 506 s, the blade reaches 90° pitch angle at 523 s, later than QB

Figure 31: Peak edgewise root bending moment (M_x) for QB (left, DLC1.4 seed 637 ECD-) and OF (right, DLC6.3 seed 10000 wave misalignment 0° , yaw 20°). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust and torque (right axis, dashed line), (f) wind speed. $\text{Max}(M_x)$ in DLC1.4, seed 638 ECD+ for DL.

and OF. This delay is caused by differences in the way an override pitch procedure can be imposed in DL. Regardless of the differences, the shutdown procedure coupled with the transient event triggers similar behaviour in the three analysed codes. Some response at the blade and tower natural frequencies can be seen in the edgewise root bending moment and nacelle fore-aft acceleration in OF. Traces of this can also be seen in DL and QB but to a much lesser extent. High-amplitude oscillations at the edgewise natural frequency can be seen in Figure 31, in DLC 6.3 where the peak loads of OF are recorded. Such instabilities were noted mostly in OF computation, sometimes even leading to crashes and incomplete simulations. The

cause of such instabilities can likely be attributed to the simpler modal-based structural model in OF.

Figure 32: SOFTWIND spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (left) Tower base force data, maxima. (right) Tower base moment data, maxima.

Tower base fore-aft and side-side forces and bending moments are shown in Figure 32. Fore-aft force (TB Fx) and bending moment (TB My) are located in DLC 1.6 with the exception of TB My for DL which is located in DLC 6.1. With this exception, fore-aft loads are in good agreement between the codes, with QB often falling between OF and DL. Side-side tower base forces are located in DLC 6.2 for all three codes, indicating that parked conditions in severe yaw-misalignment are the most severe for this load-sensor and test case combination. The dynamics that lead to fore-aft peak bending moments can be analysed in more detail in Figure 33. Peak load is shown on the left in DLC 1.6 for OF and QB. In this load case, although the shift in mean wind-speed is present for DL, all three codes agree quite well. Peak tower load occurs when platform pitch is at its peak and nacelle fore-aft acceleration is at its minimum, indicating a strong contribution to this load of inertial and gravitational loads. It must be noted that such loads are particularly significant for this test case as the tower developed for the OO-Star platform in the Lifes50+ H2020 project [15] was used, which is particularly heavy. Once again, despite the severe oscillations in aerodynamic thrust and torque, good agreement is seen between OF and QB, even when thrust is negative. As expected, rotor thrust and torque present a time-lag with respect to pitch motion and nacelle acceleration, as these metrics depend on relative wind velocity. Therefore, peak tower base bending moment occurs when thrust force is

not at its peak, but rather, differently from an onshore wind turbine, its value is approximately $1e6$ N (about 50% of peak).

Figure 33: Peak fore-aft tower base bending moment (*My*) for QB and OF (left, DLC1.6 seed 1092) and DL (right, DLC6.1 seed 10001 misalignment -30° yaw 0°). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust and torque (right axis, dashed line), (f) wind speed.

The DLC 6.1 Time series where peak-loads occur for DL are shown in Figure 33 (right). During this peak-load event, although tower base, inertial and gravitational loads remain closely tied together, all three codes behave very differently.

Figure 34: Peak edgewise side-side tower base bending moment (M_x) for QB (left, DLC6.2 seed 10002 misalignment -30° yaw 135°) and OF & DL (right, DLC6.2 seed 10002 misalignment -30° yaw 180°). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust and torque (right axis, dashed line), (f) wind speed.

Time series where side-side peak bending moments are shown in Figure 34 for OF and QB (left) and for DL (right). Once again platform roll – since this is a side-side load the side-side oscillation of the platform is plotted – and tower base load correlates nicely, as does nacelle side-side acceleration for QB and DL. For OF, nacelle acceleration is exported in a reference system that yaws with the nacelle, and therefore this output does not correspond to the one shown for QB and OF for this test case. Comparing the cases where the peak for OF and DL (right) and QB (left) are recorded, it can be noted that the dynamics of the system are very similar. The two cases differ only for yaw angle setting, and wave and wind Time series are the same. This seems

to hint to the fact that in parked conditions rotor aerodynamic loads have little influence on system dynamics. Significant differences in rotor speed between OF and QB can be seen. Unfortunately, we do not have value for DL to compare to as if control is deactivated, as is the case when the turbine is parked, control sensors cannot be output and are instead replaced by zeros. Finally, comparing Figure 34 (a) and (g) peak in TB Mx for OF appears to be in Figure 34 (a), not in Figure 34 (g). Indeed, the peak is higher in Figure 34 (a), however, due to the maximum averaging process described in section 8.1, this value is considered an outlier for OF.

Figure 35: SOFTWIND spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Blade tip deflections in blade coned (non-pitching) ref. system, maxima.

Figure 36: SOFTWIND spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Shaft loading data, maxima.

Figure 37: SOFTWIND spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (right) Generator data, maxima. (left) Aerodynamic data, maxima. Aero Thrust is defined as total aerodynamic force along rotor shaft for OF and QB, and total aerodynamic force projected along wind heading direction for DL. Large outlier in DL due to numerical instability in DLC 1.6 seed 1082.

Figure 38: SOFTWIND spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (left) Tower top forces, maxima. (right) Tower top moments, maxima.

A comparison of the extreme values, as estimated by the considered codes, for the SOFTWIND model is reported in Table 9.

Table 9. SOFTWIND model extreme value comparison.

	Type	Label	Units	Name QB	QB value	Name OF	OF value	Name DL	DL value	OF-QB diff. (%)	DL-QB diff. (%)
PtfmSurge	Min	Surge	m	6.1	-1.06E+1	1.4	-1.20E+1	1.4	-1.46E+1	13.6	38.2
	Max	Surge	m	1.6	1.92E+1	1.6	2.12E+1	6.1	2.70E+1	10.3	40.5
PtfmSway	Min	Sway	m	6.2	-1.27E+1	6.2	-1.25E+1	1.4	-9.01E+0	-1.7	-29.3
	Max	Sway	m	6.2	1.16E+1	6.2	1.40E+1	1.4	9.36E+0	21.1	-19.2
PtfmHeave	Min	Heave	m	6.2	-7.54E+0	6.1	-5.78E+0	6.2	-1.00E+1	-23.3	33.3
	Max	Heave	m	6.1	1.49E+0	6.1	3.12E+0	6.2	4.89E+0	109.4	227.5
PtfmRoll	Min	Roll	°	6.2	-7.53E+0	6.2	-8.44E+0	6.2	-5.53E+0	12.1	-26.6
	Max	Roll	°	6.2	7.67E+0	6.2	9.37E+0	6.2	5.46E+0	22.1	-28.8
PtfmPitch	Min	Pitch	°	6.1	-7.81E+0	1.4	-7.18E+0	6.2	-1.23E+1	-8.1	57.7
	Max	Pitch	°	1.6	7.71E+0	1.6	7.84E+0	6.1	1.36E+1	1.6	77.0
PtfmYaw	Min	Yaw	°	1.3	-4.60E+0	6.2	-8.75E+0	1.6	-6.56E+0	90.2	42.7
	Max	Yaw	°	6.2	4.66E+0	6.2	1.17E+1	1.3	5.72E+0	151.1	22.7
TipDxc1	Min	B1 Tip DX	m	1.4	-8.86E+0	1.4	-8.93E+0	6.2	-3.06E-01	0.9	-96.5
	Max	B1 Tip DX	m	1.6	1.39E+1	1.6	1.48E+1	6.1	2.15E-01	6.7	-98.4
TipDyc1	Min	B1 Tip DY	m	6.1	-5.04E+0	6.1	-5.10E+0	6.2	-1.31E+0	1.3	-73.9
	Max	B1 Tip DY	m	6.1	4.21E+0	1.4	4.08E+0	6.2	1.31E+0	-3.0	-68.8
RootMxb1	Min	B1 Mx	kNm	1.6	-2.04E+4	6.3	-2.68E+4	6.2	-2.10E+4	31.5	3.1
	Max	B1 Mx	kNm	1.6	1.90E+4	6.3	3.19E+4	1.3	2.27E+4	67.8	19.5
RootMyb1	Min	B1 My	kNm	1.4	-3.48E+4	1.4	-2.95E+4	1.4	-3.31E+4	-15.4	-5.1
	Max	B1 My	kNm	1.6	5.21E+4	1.6	5.39E+4	1.6	4.68E+4	3.6	-10.1
RootMxb2	Min	B2 Mx	kNm	1.6	-1.92E+4	6.3	-2.77E+4	6.1	-2.04E+4	44.1	6.1
	Max	B2 Mx	kNm	1.6	1.92E+4	6.3	3.03E+4	1.3	2.20E+4	57.5	14.6
RootMyb2	Min	B2 My	kNm	1.4	-3.09E+4	1.4	-4.43E+4	1.4	-3.36E+4	43.4	8.8
	Max	B2 My	kNm	1.6	5.23E+4	1.6	5.33E+4	1.6	4.68E+4	2.0	-10.4
RootMxb3	Min	B3 Mx	kNm	1.6	-1.99E+4	6.3	-3.01E+4	6.2	-2.05E+4	51.4	3.2
	Max	B3 Mx	kNm	1.4	2.49E+4	6.3	2.70E+4	1.4	2.95E+4	8.3	18.4
RootMyb3	Min	B3 My	kNm	1.4	-3.34E+4	1.4	-4.27E+4	1.4	-3.43E+4	27.7	2.5
	Max	B3 My	kNm	1.6	5.35E+4	1.6	5.55E+4	1.6	4.62E+4	3.8	-13.6
RootMxc1	Min	B1 Mx	kNm	6.1	-2.13E+4	6.2	-2.51E+4	6.1	-2.00E+4	18.0	-6.1
	Max	B1 Mx	kNm	6.2	2.66E+4	1.3	2.50E+4	1.6	2.43E+4	-6.1	-8.8
RootMyc1	Min	B1 My	kNm	1.4	-4.03E+4	1.4	-3.50E+4	1.6	-3.76E+4	-13.2	-6.8
	Max	B1 My	kNm	1.6	5.41E+4	1.6	5.29E+4	1.6	4.47E+4	-2.1	-17.3
RootMxc2	Min	B2 Mx	kNm	6.2	-2.60E+4	6.1	-2.09E+4	1.4	-2.05E+4	-19.8	-21.2
	Max	B2 Mx	kNm	6.1	2.25E+4	1.3	2.42E+4	1.6	2.45E+4	7.9	9.0
RootMyc2	Min	B2 My	kNm	1.4	-3.18E+4	1.4	-4.42E+4	1.6	-3.88E+4	38.8	22.0
	Max	B2 My	kNm	1.6	5.24E+4	1.6	5.33E+4	1.6	4.36E+4	1.7	-16.7

RootMxc3	Min	B3 Mx	kNm	6.2	-2.44E+4	6.1	-2.07E+4	6.2	-1.96E+4	-15.2	-19.6
	Max	B3 Mx	kNm	6.1	2.23E+4	1.3	2.51E+4	1.4	2.93E+4	12.5	31.6
RootMyc3	Min	B3 My	kNm	1.4	-4.02E+4	1.4	-4.75E+4	1.6	-3.81E+4	18.1	-5.3
	Max	B3 My	kNm	1.6	5.29E+4	1.6	5.42E+4	1.6	4.27E+4	2.3	-19.4
LSShftFxa	Min	Rot Th	kN	1.6	-1.27E+3	1.6	-1.45E+3	1.4	-1.12E+3	13.9	-12.1
	Max	Rot Th	kN	1.6	3.35E+3	1.6	3.37E+3	1.6	2.88E+3	0.8	-13.8
GenTq	Min	Gen Tq	kNm	1.6	0.00E+0	1.3	0.00E+0	6.1	0.00E+0	N/A	N/A
	Max	Gen Tq	kNm	1.6	2.21E+2	1.6	2.21E+2	1.3	2.00E+2	-0.1	-9.6
GenPwr	Min	Gen Pwr	kW	1.6	0.00E+0	1.3	0.00E+0	1.4	0.00E+0	N/A	N/A
	Max	Gen Pwr	kW	1.6	1.52E+4	1.6	1.59E+4	1.6	1.51E+4	4.2	-1.2
RtAeroFhx	Min	Aero Th	N	6.1	-1.31E+5	1.4	-1.37E+6	1.4	-9.92E+5	940.6	655.5
	Max	Aero Th	N	1.6	2.72E+6	1.6	2.78E+6	1.6	3.57E+6	2.2	31.6
RtAeroMhx	Min	Aero Tq	Nm	1.4	-2.38E+7	1.4	-2.54E+7	1.3	0.00E+0	6.7	-100.0
	Max	Aero Tq	Nm	1.6	4.29E+7	1.6	4.41E+7	1.3	0.00E+0	2.6	-100.0
YawBrFxp	Min	TT Fx	kN	1.6	-3.22E+3	1.6	-3.51E+3	6.1	-4.13E+3	9.1	28.5
	Max	TT Fx	kN	1.6	4.64E+3	1.6	4.80E+3	6.1	5.33E+3	3.4	14.7
YawBrFyp	Min	TT Fy	kN	6.2	-3.38E+3	6.3	-3.42E+3	6.2	-2.53E+3	1.1	-25.4
	Max	TT Fy	kN	6.2	3.41E+3	6.2	3.70E+3	6.2	2.44E+3	8.5	-28.3
YawBrMxp	Min	TT Mx	kNm	6.2	-9.63E+3	6.3	-2.90E+4	6.2	-9.26E+3	200.7	-3.8
	Max	TT Mx	kNm	6.2	1.81E+4	6.3	1.66E+4	1.6	1.42E+4	-8.3	-21.2
YawBrMyp	Min	TT My	kNm	1.6	-3.06E+4	1.4	-4.74E+4	1.4	-3.89E+4	54.7	27.0
	Max	TT My	kNm	1.6	3.38E+4	1.6	4.03E+4	1.6	3.53E+4	19.1	4.3
TwrBsFxt	Min	TB Fx	kN	6.1	-8.26E+3	1.6	-6.22E+3	1.6	-6.46E+3	-24.8	-21.8
	Max	TB Fx	kN	1.6	9.07E+3	1.6	8.99E+3	1.6	9.23E+3	-0.9	1.8
TwrBsFyt	Min	TB Fy	kN	6.2	-7.87E+3	6.2	-8.09E+3	6.2	-5.52E+3	2.8	-29.9
	Max	TB Fy	kN	6.2	7.71E+3	6.2	8.57E+3	6.2	5.47E+3	11.2	-29.1
TwrBsMxt	Min	TB Mx	kNm	6.2	-5.33E+5	6.2	-5.67E+5	6.2	-3.84E+5	6.4	-27.9
	Max	TB Mx	kNm	6.2	5.41E+5	6.2	5.33E+5	6.2	3.90E+5	-1.5	-27.9
TwrBsMyt	Min	TB My	kNm	6.1	-5.94E+5	1.6	-4.66E+5	6.1	-6.56E+5	-21.4	10.4
	Max	TB My	kNm	1.6	6.73E+5	1.6	6.41E+5	6.1	8.40E+5	-4.7	24.7
FAIRTEN1	Min	FAIRTEN1	kN	1.6	6.62E+2	1.6	6.20E+2	6.1	-5.52E+0	-6.4	-100.8
	Max	FAIRTEN1	kN	6.1	5.18E+3	1.6	3.87E+3	6.1	4.64E+3	-25.2	-10.4
FAIRTEN2	Min	FAIRTEN2	kN	6.1	1.35E+3	6.2	5.69E+2	6.2	4.54E+0	-57.9	-99.7
	Max	FAIRTEN2	kN	6.2	6.05E+3	6.2	5.49E+3	6.2	4.94E+3	-9.2	-18.4
FAIRTEN3	Min	FAIRTEN3	kN	6.1	1.30E+3	6.2	5.85E+2	6.2	3.07E+1	-55.2	-97.6
	Max	FAIRTEN3	kN	6.2	6.04E+3	6.2	6.85E+3	6.1	5.84E+3	13.4	-3.3

An indication of the average differences between the codes is shown in Table 10, separately for overpredictions and underpredictions.

Table 10. Average code-to-code differences, SOFTWIND model

	OF-QB	DL-QB
average + diff	24.06%	51.76%
average - diff	-14.21%	-29.22%

8.3 OC4 MODEL EXTREME VALUE ANALYSIS

An analysis of extreme loads recorded for the OC4 model is shown in this section. Mean-of-max values (IEC 61400-1 appendix I) are shown in the bars, while absolute maximum values with no averaging are shown in the corresponding diamonds. In-detail Time series analysis are provided for key load-sensor for an in-depth analysis of the physics leading to the peak loads on the components.

Figure 39: OC4 spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Platform motion data, maxima.

Peaks in platform motions appear to agree well, with the exception of surge, which however remains in the same DLC for both OF and QB (Figure 39).

Blade root flapwise, edgewise, in-plane and out-of-plane root loads are shown in Figure 40. Flapwise loads are in very good agreement. OF underestimated QB approximately 2-4% depending on which blade is considered. DLC 1.3 (normal operation in extreme turbulence) generates the highest flapwise loads for both codes on all three blades. Edgewise loads on the other hand are not in good agreement. As will be shown in detail in the following this is due to an edgewise blade resonance in parked conditions for OF. This can be noted in Figure 40 looking at the outliers for OF, that are very high. Because the outliers are referred to DLC 6.2, where the turbine is parked and the blades are pitched to 90°, they are also apparent in the out-of-plane peak loads. Time series relative to the recorded peaks in blade root flapwise bending moment (BR Myb) in QB and OF are shown in Figure 41 (a-f) and (g-l), respectively. As mentioned previously, for this test case peak BR Myb is recorded in DLC 1.3, in simulations near rated, with 11 m/s mean wind speed.

Figure 40: OC4 spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (top) Blade root moment data in blade ref. system, maxima. (bottom) Blade root moment data in blade non-pitching ref. system, maxima.

BR Myb is mainly influenced by aerodynamic loads and thus depends on the relative inflow velocity. Because of wind shear, the local azimuth of each blade will influence loads significantly and since QB and OF predict different rotor speeds, blade azimuth will be different in the two codes. Figure 41 (d,j) shows how rotor speed is higher for QB when wind speed dips below rated. This characteristic is noted in all three models (Figure 6, Figure 13, Figure 23) and also in previous code-to-code comparisons in onshore conditions [33]. In practice, this implies that the Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) is higher for QB, leading to higher aerodynamic thrust (Figure 41 (e, k)). The higher thrust seems to be influencing platform pitch, that is on average higher for QB thrust (Figure 41 (b, h)). Despite this, overall, blade root bending moments are very similar in magnitude, as if we consider the maximum value of BR My on all three blades OF is only 1% higher than QB (Table 12).

Figure 41: Peak flapwise blade root bending moment (My) for QB (left, DLC1.3 seed 638) and OF (right, DLC1.3 seed 634). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust (f) wind speed.

Time histories in correspondence with blade root edgewise peak loads are shown in Figure 42. For this sensor, the DLC where peak loading occurs is not the same: DLC 1.4 for QB and DLC 6.2 for OF. These correspond respectively to operation with extreme direction change and parked in Extreme Sea State (ESS) with grid loss. Focusing on DLC 1.4 first, QB and OF behave very similarly in terms of rotor speed, blade pitch and aerodynamic thrust. The strong variation in aerodynamic thrust in correspondence with the transient wind gust event and subsequent shutdown is predicted quite well by the DBEM routine in OF if compared to the higher fidelity LLFW model in QB. Once the rotor reaches a full stop, high frequency edgewise oscillations in blade root bending moment can be seen for OF in Figure 42 (a). In QB these oscillations are

much better damped. The same can be said for the tower. In fact, looking at tower fore-aft acceleration, it is apparent how OF exhibits large and less damped oscillations at the tower's natural frequency (Figure 42 (c)). These oscillations only become relevant once the rotor is parked and aerodynamic fore-aft damping is missing. Now analysing DLC 6.2 (Figure 42 (g-l)), a clear edgewise blade resonance in OF can be seen. This leads to peak loads that are nearly three times those recorded in QB. Instability at the system's natural frequencies was noted multiple times in OF (Figure 31) and also influences fatigue loads (Figure 80) and is most likely linked to the fact that OF uses a lower-fidelity modal based structural model.

Figure 42: Peak edgewise blade root bending moment (Mx) for QB (left, DLC1.4 seed 638) and OF (right, DLC6.2 seed 10002 mis 30° yaw 45°). (b) Platform pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust (f) wind speed.

Figure 43: OC4 spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (left) Tower base force data, maxima. (right) Tower base moment data, maxima.

Predicted tower base peak loads are very similar in the two codes (Figure 43). As shown in Table 11, the fore-aft force (TB Fx) is 7% lower for OF, the tower base side-side bending moment (TB Mx) is 18% lower, and the tower base side-side force (TB Fy) and fore-aft bending moments (TB My) are 0.4% and 1.2% lower, respectively.

Time series in proximity of the extreme recorded TB My are shown in Figure 44. In both codes the extreme value is recorded in Severe Sea State (SSS) conditions (DLC 1.6) at an average wind speed of 23 m/s. In this condition, the higher rotor speed for QB that was visible in Figure 41 (d, j) is not present, and aerodynamic thrust is quite similar in the two codes. Similar to the Softwind test case, the TB My signal correlates quite well with the platform pitch Time series; this is an indication that hydrodynamic loading is the main driver of tower base bending moment on this test case too. In both Figure 41 (a) and (g) oscillations around the tower's natural frequency of approximately 0.4 Hz can also be noted, more marked for OF than QB.

Figure 44: Peak fore-aft tower base bending moment (M_y) for QB (left, DLC1.6 seed 1098) and OF (right, DLC1.6 seed 1095) (b) Platform pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust (f) wind speed.

Finally, Time series in proximity of peak TB M_x are shown in Figure 45. For both codes peak loads are recorded in parked conditions, in presence of grid loss (DLC 6.2), and large platform motions appear to be the main contributor to the peak loading. Very good agreement for this test case in parked conditions is noted between QB and OF in both Figure 44 and Figure 45, a slight exception being the increased variability in aerodynamic thrust that is noted for QB in Figure 45. It must be noted however that with respect to the operating conditions (Figure 41), the absolute values of rotor thrust are quite small.

Figure 45: Peak side-side tower base bending moment (M_x) for QB (left, DLC6.2 seed 10003 mis 30° yaw 90°) and OF (right, DLC6.2 seed 10002 mis -30° yaw 90°) (b) Platform pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust (f) wind speed.

Figure 46: OC4 spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Blade tip deflections in blade non-pitching ref. system, maxima.

Figure 47: OC4 spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (left) Generator data, maxima. (middle) Aerodynamic data, maxima. (right) Total thrust force along rotor shaft.

Figure 48: OC4 spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Tower top loading data, maxima.

Figure 49: OC4 spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Mooring data, maxima.

A comparison of the extreme values, as estimated by the considered codes, for the OC4 model is reported in Table 11.

Table 11. OC4 model extreme value comparison.

	Type	Label	Units	DLC QB	QB value	DLC OF	OF value	OF-QB diff. (%)
PtfmSurge	Min	Surge	m	6.1	-6.95E+00	6.1	-8.96E+00	28.87
	Max	Surge	m	6.1	1.71E+01	6.1	1.56E+01	-9.22
PtfmSway	Min	Sway	m	6.2	-7.24E+00	6.2	-7.17E+00	-0.85
	Max	Sway	m	1.4	6.52E+00	1.4	6.70E+00	2.77
PtfmHeave	Min	Heave	m	6.2	-1.11E+01	6.2	-1.02E+01	-8.22
	Max	Heave	m	6.2	1.12E+01	6.2	1.14E+01	2.05
PtfmRoll	Min	Roll	°	6.2	-5.03E+00	6.2	-4.51E+00	-10.30
	Max	Roll	°	6.2	5.06E+00	6.2	4.51E+00	-10.97
PtfmPitch	Min	Pitch	°	6.1	-9.60E+00	6.1	-8.58E+00	-10.69
	Max	Pitch	°	6.2	9.45E+00	6.2	9.24E+00	-2.16
PtfmYaw	Min	Yaw	°	6.1	-8.34E+00	6.1	-8.44E+00	1.13
	Max	Yaw	°	6.2	4.97E+00	6.2	4.66E+00	-6.21
TipDxc1	Min	B1 Tip DX	m	1.4	-9.06E+00	1.4	-8.92E+00	-1.52
	Max	B1 Tip DX	m	1.6	7.35E+00	1.3	7.07E+00	-3.75
TipDyc1	Min	B1 Tip DY	m	6.1	-3.95E+00	6.2	-4.02E+00	1.75
	Max	B1 Tip DY	m	1.4	3.56E+00	1.4	4.81E+00	35.19
RootMxb1	Min	B1 Mx	kNm	1.6	-5.71E+03	6.2	-1.94E+04	239.80
	Max	B1 Mx	kNm	1.4	9.14E+03	6.2	1.82E+04	99.50
RootMyb1	Min	B1 My	kNm	1.4	-1.72E+04	1.4	-1.63E+04	-5.21
	Max	B1 My	kNm	1.3	1.37E+04	1.3	1.43E+04	4.28
RootMxb2	Min	B2 Mx	kNm	1.3	-5.53E+03	6.2	-1.80E+04	226.25
	Max	B2 Mx	kNm	1.4	6.60E+03	1.4	8.79E+03	33.20
RootMyb2	Min	B2 My	kNm	1.4	-1.50E+04	1.4	-1.30E+04	-13.13
	Max	B2 My	kNm	1.3	1.41E+04	1.3	1.36E+04	-4.05
RootMxb3	Min	B3 Mx	kNm	1.3	-5.67E+03	6.2	-1.33E+04	134.21
	Max	B3 Mx	kNm	1.3	6.06E+03	6.2	1.49E+04	146.46
RootMyb3	Min	B3 My	kNm	1.4	-1.50E+04	1.4	-1.65E+04	9.78
	Max	B3 My	kNm	1.3	1.39E+04	1.3	1.41E+04	1.67
RootMxc1	Min	B1 Mx	kNm	6.2	-8.35E+03	1.4	-6.95E+03	-16.86
	Max	B1 Mx	kNm	1.3	8.39E+03	6.2	9.78E+03	16.51
RootMyc1	Min	B1 My	kNm	1.4	-1.88E+04	1.4	-1.74E+04	-7.52
	Max	B1 My	kNm	1.6	1.36E+04	1.3	1.42E+04	4.75
RootMxc2	Min	B2 Mx	kNm	6.1	-6.84E+03	6.2	-8.75E+03	27.95
	Max	B2 Mx	kNm	1.3	8.52E+03	1.4	1.08E+04	26.71
RootMyc2	Min	B2 My	kNm	1.4	-1.59E+04	1.4	-1.55E+04	-2.60
	Max	B2 My	kNm	1.3	1.41E+04	1.3	1.36E+04	-3.74
RootMxc3	Min	B3 Mx	kNm	6.2	-7.01E+03	6.2	-8.90E+03	26.94
	Max	B3 Mx	kNm	1.3	8.41E+03	1.3	8.67E+03	3.10

RootMyc3	Min	B3 My	kNm	1.4	-1.46E+04	1.4	-1.70E+04	16.64
	Max	B3 My	kNm	1.3	1.39E+04	1.3	1.35E+04	-2.89
LSShftFxa	Min	Rot Th	kN	1.4	-5.48E+02	1.4	-5.42E+02	-1.18
	Max	Rot Th	kN	1.4	1.08E+03	1.4	1.05E+03	-2.58
GenTq	Min	Gen Tq	kNm	1.4	0.00E+00	1.3	0.00E+00	N/A
	Max	Gen Tq	kNm	1.6	4.31E+01	1.3	4.31E+01	0.00
GenPwr	Min	Gen Pwr	kW	1.4	0.00E+00	1.4	-9.67E+02	N/A
	Max	Gen Pwr	kW	1.6	6.71E+03	1.6	6.96E+03	3.69
RtAeroFhx	Min	Aero Th	N	1.4	-6.18E+05	1.4	-6.03E+05	-2.44
	Max	Aero Th	N	1.4	8.88E+05	1.4	8.53E+05	-3.92
RtAeroMhx	Min	Aero Tq	Nm	1.4	-9.86E+06	1.4	-1.02E+07	3.62
	Max	Aero Tq	Nm	1.6	1.20E+07	1.6	1.13E+07	-5.56
YawBrFxp	Min	TT Fx	kN	6.1	-1.31E+03	6.1	-9.93E+02	-24.26
	Max	TT Fx	kN	1.6	1.42E+03	1.6	1.44E+03	1.47
YawBrFyp	Min	TT Fy	kN	6.2	-8.04E+02	6.2	-7.27E+02	-9.57
	Max	TT Fy	kN	6.2	6.92E+02	6.2	6.88E+02	-0.66
TwrBsFxt	Min	TB Fx	kN	6.1	-1.69E+03	6.1	-1.26E+03	-25.15
	Max	TB Fx	kN	6.2	2.03E+03	6.2	1.89E+03	-6.94
TwrBsFyt	Min	TB Fy	kN	6.2	-1.16E+03	6.2	-1.01E+03	-13.16
	Max	TB Fy	kN	6.2	9.84E+02	6.2	9.80E+02	-0.38
TwrBsMxt	Min	TB Mx	kNm	6.2	-6.54E+04	6.2	-6.26E+04	-4.19
	Max	TB Mx	kNm	6.2	7.94E+04	6.2	6.46E+04	-18.54
TwrBsMyt	Min	TB My	kNm	6.1	-1.20E+05	6.1	-8.96E+04	-25.41
	Max	TB My	kNm	1.6	1.32E+05	1.6	1.31E+05	-1.20
FAIRTEN1	Min	FAIRTEN1	kN	6.2	4.68E+01	6.2	1.44E+02	208.32
	Max	FAIRTEN1	kN	6.2	2.12E+03	6.2	2.36E+03	11.14
FAIRTEN2	Min	FAIRTEN2	kN	1.6	0.00E+00	6.1	5.98E-01	N/A
	Max	FAIRTEN2	kN	6.1	6.00E+03	6.1	5.70E+03	-4.96
FAIRTEN3	Min	FAIRTEN3	kN	6.2	1.11E+02	6.2	1.41E+02	28.04
	Max	FAIRTEN3	kN	6.1	2.22E+03	6.1	2.35E+03	5.68

An indication of the average differences between the codes for OC4 model can be represented in Table 12, separately for overpredictions and underpredictions.

Table 12. Average code-to-code differences, OC4 model

	OF-QB
average + diff.	44.06%
average - diff.	-8.21%

8.4 HEXAFLOAT MODEL EXTREME VALUE ANALYSIS

A comparison between the data described in the previous section is reported for the Hexafloat model. As shown in Figure 50, extreme values of platform motion are in good agreement, in both magnitude and DLC in which they are recorded.

Figure 50: HEXAFLOAT spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Platform motion data, maxima.

Blade root bending moments are also generally in good agreement. With respect to QB however, DL shows an underprediction of approximately 8% in flapwise loads and an overprediction of approximately 4.5% in edgewise loads (Table 12). Flapwise loads, which are the most influenced by aerodynamics, peak in DLC 1.6 for QB and in a mix of DLC 1.3 and 1.6 for DL, indicating that the two DLCs are very close in blade extreme loads for this test case. Time series where peak loads are recorded are shown in Figure 52 (left) for DL and (right) for QB. In both cases the platform pitch signals show the system is oscillating around its natural frequency with a period of approximately 55 s. A time-shift in the oscillation can be seen, with QB lagging DL. This is likely due to the approximately 12s shift in windspeed that can be seen in Figure 52 (f). These slow natural-frequency oscillations cause variations in relative windspeed which cause the slow-varying oscillation in flapwise moments observable both in DLC 1.3 and in DLC 1.6. Regarding Figure 52 (left), apart from the mentioned time-shift the two codes behave similarly, and a similar peak value is recorded in both cases.

Figure 51: HEXAFLOAT spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (top) Blade root moment data in blade ref. system, maxima. (bottom) Blade root moment data in blade non-pitching ref. system, maxima.

This changes in DLC 1.6 Figure 52 (right), where maximum for QB is recorded. In this case the platform pitch combines negatively with the wave elevation for QB. In fact, a wave train of relatively high intensity hits the turbine around 1010 s – 1040 s, when the platform is near its peak value of pitch for QB. On the other hand, in DL platform pitch is already decreasing when the wave train hits, therefore relative windspeed is high and, to counteract this, the blades are pitched out slightly, and therefore the wave train causes lower flapwise loads.

Figure 52: Peak flapwise root bending moment (M_y) for DL (left, DLC1.3 seed 632) and QB (right, DLC1.6 seed 1045). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust, (f) wind speed.

Blade root edgewise peak loads are located in DLC 6.1 for DL (Figure 53, left) and in DLC 1.4 for QB (Figure 53, right). In both cases the dynamics are well reproduced by the codes, platform pitch is similar and nacelle acceleration appears to be roughly in phase and at a similar frequency to the incoming waves. The phase shift in platform pitch that can be seen in DLC 1.4 (Figure 53, right) is due to the difference in the shutdown procedure in the two codes (Figure 53 (e)), which also leads to different maximum edgewise loads being predicted.

Figure 53: Peak edgewise root bending moment (My) for DL (left, DLC6.1 seed 10001 mis-30 y10) and QB (right, DLC1.4 seed 619). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust, (f) wind speed.

Tower base extreme fore-aft bending moments are shown in Figure 54. Good agreement in shear forces both in magnitude and DLC can be noted. The same can be said for bending moments although the DLC where the peak side-side bending moment is not the same. Time series for the fore-aft tower base loads are shown in Figure 55. In both cases peak loading occurs in DLC 1.6. Once again low-frequency oscillations in pitch can be seen. These oscillations however do not appear to influence the nacelle fore-aft acceleration signals, since the time-lag between QB and DL that is observable in the former is not observable in the latter. Nacelle acceleration appears to be driven by oscillations at the wave frequency. As it was the case for the other test cases (SOFTWIND, OC4), the peak loads occur when the fore-aft acceleration and

the platform pitch are in an unfavourable combination, maximising inertial and gravitational loads. However, mean pitch appears to influence the fore-aft bending moment less than in the previously discussed test cases, as can be noted by the weaker correlation between fore-aft bending moment and platform pitch. This is possibly due to the fact that in this test case the standard onshore tower for the DTU 10MW RWT is used which is much lighter than the OO-Star platform tower used in the SOFTWIND test case. Finally, although the control signals are quite different - because of the different platform motion and consequently different relative inflow velocity – rotor thrust is quite similar.

Figure 54: HEXAFLOAT spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (left) Tower base force data, maxima. (right) Tower base moment data, maxima.

Figure 55: Peak fore-aft tower base bending moment (M_y) for DL (left, DLC1.6 seed 1038) and QB (right, DLC1.6 seed 1035). (b) Platform Pitch, (c) nacelle fore-aft acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust, (f) wind speed.

Tower base side-side extreme loads are shown in Figure 56 for DL (left) and QB (right). In both cases they are recorded in DLC 6.2. In absence of significant rotor aerodynamic loads, platform roll and side-side bending moment signals show much better alignment. In fact, the rotor is yawed 90° out of the wind with feathered blades and thus contributes only marginally to side-side loads. For QB (Figure 56, right) peak loading is caused by a low-frequency oscillation, around the roll natural frequency. On the other hand, for DL peak loads are generated by a much higher frequency oscillation.

Figure 56: Peak side-side tower base bending moment (M_x) for DL (left, DLC6.2 seed 10000 mis30 y90) and QB (right, DLC6.2 seed 10003 mis30 y90). (b) Platform Roll, (c) nacelle side-sides acceleration and wave elevation (right axis, dashed line), (d) blade pitch and rotor speed (right axis, dashed lines), (e) rotor aero thrust, (f) wind speed.

Figure 57: HEXAFLOAT spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (left) Generator data, maxima. (right) Rotor thrust along low speed shaft.

Figure 58: HEXAFLOAT spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. (right) Tower top loading data.

Figure 59: HEXAFLOAT spar floater aggregate extreme value analysis. Mooring data, maxima.

A comparison of the extreme values, as estimated by the considered codes, for the SOFTWIND model is reported in Table 13.

Table 13. HEXAFLOAT model extreme value comparison.

	Type	Label	Units	DLC QB	QB value	DLC DL	DL value	DL-QB diff. (%)
PtfmSurge	Min	Surge	m	1.4	-1.44E+01	1.4	-1.55E+01	7.46%
	Max	Surge	m	1.3	9.86E+01	6.2	9.84E+01	-0.24%
PtfmSway	Min	Sway	m	1.4	-4.58E+01	1.4	-5.01E+01	9.52%
	Max	Sway	m	1.4	4.62E+01	1.4	5.00E+01	8.36%
PtfmHeave	Min	Heave	m	6.2	-6.59E+00	6.2	-7.39E+00	12.15%
	Max	Heave	m	6.1	5.77E+00	6.1	4.99E+00	-13.52%
PtfmRoll	Min	Roll	deg	1.4	-4.47E+00	1.4	-4.40E+00	-1.46%
	Max	Roll	deg	1.4	4.03E+00	6.1	6.71E+00	66.60%
PtfmPitch	Min	Pitch	deg	1.4	-9.37E+00	1.4	-8.43E+00	-10.02%
	Max	Pitch	deg	1.3	1.04E+01	1.3	9.66E+00	-7.30%
PtfmYaw	Min	Yaw	deg	1.3	-1.46E+01	1.3	-1.38E+01	-5.66%
	Max	Yaw	deg	1.6	1.19E+01	1.3	9.44E+00	-20.62%
TipDxc1	Min	B1 Tip DX	m	1.4	-1.12E+01	1.3	0.00E+00	

	Max	B1 Tip DX	m	1.6	1.16E+01	1.3	0.00E+00	
TipDyc1	Min	B1 Tip DY	m	6.1	-5.00E+00	1.3	0.00E+00	
	Max	B1 Tip DY	m	1.4	3.80E+00	1.3	0.00E+00	
RootMxb1	Min	B1 Root Mx	kNm	1.6	-1.70E+04	6.2	-2.76E+04	62.01%
	Max	B1 Root Mx	kNm	1.4	3.08E+04	6.1	3.22E+04	4.59%
RootMyb1	Min	B1 Root My	kNm	1.4	-3.99E+04	1.4	-2.96E+04	-25.81%
	Max	B1 Root My	kNm	1.6	4.33E+04	1.3	3.86E+04	-10.79%
RootMxb2	Min	B2 Root Mx	kNm	1.3	-1.71E+04	6.1	-2.48E+04	45.17%
	Max	B2 Root Mx	kNm	1.4	2.14E+04	6.2	2.55E+04	19.32%
RootMyb2	Min	B2 Root My	kNm	1.4	-4.62E+04	1.4	-3.15E+04	-31.76%
	Max	B2 Root My	kNm	1.6	4.24E+04	1.6	3.88E+04	-8.39%
RootMxb3	Min	B3 Root Mx	kNm	1.6	-1.89E+04	6.2	-2.60E+04	37.54%
	Max	B3 Root Mx	kNm	1.4	2.66E+04	6.1	3.19E+04	19.99%
RootMyb3	Min	B3 Root My	kNm	1.4	-3.92E+04	1.4	-3.18E+04	-19.06%
	Max	B3 Root My	kNm	1.6	4.25E+04	1.3	3.93E+04	-7.61%
RootMxc1	Min	B1 Root Mx fix	kNm	6.1	-2.08E+04	6.1	-2.31E+04	10.80%
	Max	B1 Root Mx fix	kNm	6.2	2.61E+04	1.3	2.51E+04	-3.61%
RootMyc1	Min	B1 Root My fix	kNm	1.4	-4.80E+04	1.3	-3.55E+04	-26.05%
	Max	B1 Root My fix	kNm	1.6	4.33E+04	1.6	3.77E+04	-13.03%
RootMxc2	Min	B2 Root Mx fix	kNm	6.2	-2.25E+04	6.1	-2.36E+04	5.10%
	Max	B2 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.6	2.26E+04	1.3	2.44E+04	7.71%
RootMyc2	Min	B2 Root My fix	kNm	1.4	-5.05E+04	1.3	-3.59E+04	-28.93%
	Max	B2 Root My fix	kNm	1.6	4.24E+04	1.6	3.68E+04	-13.08%
RootMxc3	Min	B3 Root Mx fix	kNm	6.2	-2.33E+04	6.1	-2.44E+04	4.53%
	Max	B3 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.6	2.21E+04	1.3	2.50E+04	13.22%
RootMyc3	Min	B3 Root My fix	kNm	1.4	-4.37E+04	1.3	-3.58E+04	-18.20%
	Max	B3 Root My fix	kNm	1.6	4.25E+04	1.6	3.68E+04	-13.49%
LSShftFxa	Max	RotThrust	kN	1.6	2.68E+03	1.6	2.54E+03	-5.51%
	Max	RotThrust	kN	1.6	2.68E+03	1.6	2.54E+03	-5.51%
	Min	RotThrust	kN	1.4	-1.22E+03	1.4	-4.85E+02	-60.31%
	Min	RotThrust	kN	1.4	-1.22E+03	1.4	-4.85E+02	-60.31%
GenTq	Min	Gen Tq	kNm	1.4	0.00E+00	6.1	0.00E+00	
	Max	Gen Tq	kNm	1.3	2.00E+02	1.3	2.00E+02	0.00%
GenPwr	Min	Gen Pwr	kW	1.4	0.00E+00	6.1	0.00E+00	
	Max	Gen Pwr	kW	1.6	1.35E+04	1.3	1.43E+04	5.53%

RtAeroFhx	Min	Aero Thrust	kN	1.4	-1.51E+06	1.4	-8.77E+05	-41.83%
	Max	Aero Thrust	kN	1.6	2.09E+06	1.3	5.50E+06	162.53%
RtAeroMxh	Min	Aero Torque	kNm	1.4	-2.92E+07	1.3	0.00E+00	
	Max	Aero Torque	kNm	1.6	3.16E+07	1.3	0.00E+00	
YawBrFxp	Min	TT Fx	kN	1.4	-2.86E+03	1.4	-1.79E+03	-37.38%
	Max	TT Fx	kN	1.6	3.58E+03	1.6	3.60E+03	0.68%
YawBrFyp	Min	TT Fy	kN	6.2	-1.95E+03	6.1	-2.20E+03	12.87%
	Max	TT Fy	kN	1.4	1.02E+03	6.2	1.53E+03	50.12%
TwrBsFxt	Min	TB Fx	kN	1.4	-3.88E+03	1.4	-2.62E+03	-32.48%
	Max	TB Fx	kN	1.6	4.72E+03	1.6	4.73E+03	0.14%
TwrBsFyt	Min	TB Fy	kN	6.2	-2.69E+03	6.1	-2.94E+03	9.24%
	Max	TB Fy	kN	1.4	1.73E+03	1.4	1.80E+03	3.64%
TwrBsMxt	Min	TB Mx	kNm	1.4	-1.58E+05	1.4	-1.64E+05	3.55%
	Max	TB Mx	kNm	6.2	2.72E+05	6.1	2.87E+05	5.52%
TwrBsMyt	Min	TB My	kNm	1.4	-4.09E+05	1.4	-2.50E+05	-38.89%
	Max	TB My	kNm	1.6	4.76E+05	1.6	4.60E+05	-3.34%
TendTens1	Min	TendTens1	N	1.6	2.57E+03	1.6	4.44E+03	72.62%
	Max	TendTens1	N	1.4	9.70E+06	6.1	8.77E+06	-9.60%
TendTens2	Min	TendTens2	N	1.6	1.09E+06	6.2	5.82E+05	-46.46%
	Max	TendTens2	N	1.4	7.91E+06	6.1	8.48E+06	7.25%
TendTens3	Min	TendTens3	N	1.4	1.41E+06	1.4	2.05E+06	45.67%
	Max	TendTens3	N	6.2	9.72E+06	6.1	9.74E+06	0.24%
TendTens4	Min	TendTens4	N	1.4	3.08E+05	1.4	1.90E+06	516.16%
	Max	TendTens4	N	1.6	1.18E+07	6.2	1.20E+07	1.96%
TendTens5	Min	TendTens5	N	1.4	2.02E+06	1.4	2.09E+06	3.45%
	Max	TendTens5	N	6.2	8.77E+06	6.2	1.01E+07	15.33%
TendTens6	Min	TendTens6	N	1.6	9.05E+05	6.1	7.67E+05	-15.32%
	Max	TendTens6	N	1.4	8.57E+06	1.4	7.72E+06	-9.96%

An indication of the average differences between the codes for OC4 model can be represented in Table 14, separately for overpredictions and underpredictions.

Table 14. Average code-to-code differences, HEXAFLOAT model

	DL-QB
average + diff.	35.73%
average - diff.	-19.56%

9 FATIGUE ANALYSIS

9.1 METHODS AND TOOLS

The Matlab based tool MLife [32] developed by NREL is used in the computation of fatigue loads. As mentioned in section 7, this code is primarily intended to perform a fatigue analysis. In this work, in order to compare the results of multiple codes with respect to fatigue related issues, the Damage Equivalent Loads (DELs) are considered. This metric allows to represent the effect of a full stochastic load time history [32,37]. A DEL is defined as the load range which produces, over a given number of loading cycles n^{eq} , the same fatigue effect of a given load time history. A rainflow counting algorithm is used to determine the number of load cycles in each time history, contained in each file of the dataset. For the j -th file the short-term DEL can be expressed according to the following relation:

$$DEL_j = \left(\sum_i \frac{n_{ji}(L_{ji})^m}{n^{eq}} \right)^{1/m}$$

where L_{ji} is the i -th load cycle found by the rainflow algorithm, n_{ji} is the corresponding number of cycles, n^{eq} the equivalent number of loading cycles and m is the so-called *fatigue exponent*, characteristic of the used material. In this work the number of equivalent cycles is set by the time duration of the simulation file, assuming a 1 Hz equivalent loading cycle frequency. For each file a short-term DEL is estimated (with a number of equivalent cycles n^{eq} equal to 1800). Lifetime DELs are computed based on the 1 Hz DELs considering 907200 cycles, corresponding to the total amount of simulated time with 1 Hz cyclic loading frequency. Damage equivalent loads are presented as a function of wind speed after a binning procedure similar to the one used for the postprocessing of the statistical data.

Table 15. Fatigue exponents

Load group	Assumed material	Fatigue exponent
Blade root (Blades 1-3)	Fibre reinforced composite	10
Tower top actions	Steel	4
Tower base actions	Steel	4
Shaft loadings	Steel	4
Mooring loads	Steel (Chain)	4

The DELs are grouped based on loading location, as described in Table 16. DELs data are reported for fixed fatigue exponent values, for each considered group of loads, according to the list in Table 15. The choice of such values for the fatigue exponent is based on typically used materials for each considered component.

Table 16. Variable considered for DEL analysis.

Data group	Variable considered for fatigue analysis			
		Blade 1	Blade 2	Blade 3
Blade root in blade reference system (sec. 5.4) (This coord. sys. is denoted using the subscript "b")	Blade root edgewise moment	<i>RootMxb1</i>	<i>RootMxb2</i>	<i>RootMxb3</i>
	Blade root flapwise moment	<i>RootMyb1</i>	<i>RootMyb2</i>	<i>RootMyb3</i>
	Blade root pitching moment	<i>RootMzb1</i>	<i>RootMzb2</i>	<i>RootMzb3</i>
Blade root in coned reference system (sec. 5.4) (This coord. sys. is denoted using the subscript "c")	Blade root edgewise moment	<i>RootMxc1</i>	<i>RootMxc2</i>	<i>RootMxc3</i>
	Blade root flapwise moment	<i>RootMyc1</i>	<i>RootMyc2</i>	<i>RootMyc3</i>
	Blade root pitching moment	<i>RootMzc1</i>	<i>RootMzc2</i>	<i>RootMzc3</i>
Tower top actions	Tower top fore-aft force <i>TwrBsFxt</i> Tower top side-side force <i>TwrBsFyt</i> Tower top vertical force <i>TwrBsFzt</i> Tower top side-side moment <i>TwrBsMxt</i> Tower top fore-aft moment <i>TwrBsMyt</i> Tower top torsional moment <i>TwrBsMzt</i>			
Tower base actions	Tower base fore-aft force <i>YawBrFxp</i> Tower base side-side force <i>YawBrFyp</i> Tower base vertical force <i>YawBrFzp</i> Tower base side-side moment <i>YawBrMxp</i> Tower base fore-aft moment <i>YawBrMyp</i> Tower base torsional moment <i>YawBrMzp</i>			
Shaft loadings	Shaft axial force (in rotating ref. system) <i>LSShftFxa</i>			
Mooring loads	Fairlead tensions (3 lines for SOFTWIND and OC4) <i>FAIRTEN</i> Tendon tensions (6 lines for HEXAFLOAT) <i>TendTens</i>			

The DELs are calculated for each simulation in DLC1.2. Results reported in two different forms:

- the aggregated Lifetime DELs: the results for each velocity are combined, based on the assumed environmental probability distribution, yielding the overall DEL referred to the

whole FOWT lifetime; Lifetime DELs data are presented in histograms, comparing the results for each considered load as computed by each code;

- to get a deeper insight on the results from the different codes, the calculated DELs are also grouped by wind speed and reported using a boxplot diagram for each group of loads; the boxplot reports the median value (inner line), the interquartile range (filled box), the maximum range (whiskers) from the DELs calculated at a given wind speed (possible outliers are defined as points differing from the interquartile range limits more than 1.5 times the interquartile range; outliers are not reported to improve graph clarity).

As for extreme loads, blade root flapwise and edgewise bending moments as well as tower base fore-aft and side-side bending moments are commented in detail. Power Spectral Density (PSD) plots of these load sensors are also shown to give an understanding of the phenomena that influence fatigue loading on the three test cases. Further observations are discussed in section 9.

9.2 COMPARISON OF DAMAGE EQUIVALENT LOADS FOR THE SOFTWIND MODEL

9.2.1 Lifetime DELs comparison (SOFTWIND)

A comparison of the Lifetime DELs are reported for the SOFTWIND model in the following figures, for different sets of load components.

As shown in Figure 60, blade root DELs estimated using OF are approximately 17% higher than QB in the flapwise direction and 3% higher in the edgewise direction. DL on the other hand predicts edgewise loads that are very close to QB while underestimating flapwise DELs by approximately 5%. In the coned reference system (Figure 60), DL predictions differ greatly from OF and QB.

Tower top and tower base DELs are shown in Figure 61 and Figure 62. While tower top moments are in good agreement between the three codes, and OF and DL both predict higher lifetime DELs than QB, tower top forces and tower base forces and bending moments do not show the same good agreement. Respect to QB, fore-aft loads appear to be higher for DL and lower for OF. Side-side loads on the other hand are lower than QB for DL and higher for OF. Moreover, in the case of OF, side-side DELs are greater than fore-aft DELs. This will be discussed in more detail in section 9.2.2.

Figure 60: SOFTWIND spar floater Lifetime DELs. (left) Blade 1 root data in blade ref. system. (right) Blade 1 root data in non-pitching ref. system.

Figure 61: SOFTWIND spar floater Lifetime DELs. Tower top data.

Figure 62: SOFTWIND spar floater Lifetime DELs. Tower base data.

Figure 63: SOFTWIND spar floater Lifetime DELs. Mooring loads.

Table 17. Lifetime DELs for key load sensors for the SOFTWIND model. Percentage difference of OF and DL values with respect to QB predictions in the right column.

sensor	Label	Units	QB	OF	DL	OF-QB diff. (%)	DL-QB diff. (%)
RootMxb1	B1 Root Mx	kNm	1.83E+04	1.89E+04	1.83E+04	3.26%	-0.26%
RootMyb1	B1 Root My	kNm	1.73E+04	2.01E+04	1.65E+04	16.69%	-4.63%
RootMzb1	B1 Root Mz	kNm	2.95E+02	3.69E+02	6.22E+02	25.21%	111.07%
RootMxb2	B2 Root Mx	kNm	1.83E+04	1.89E+04	1.83E+04	3.27%	-0.23%
RootMyb2	B2 Root My	kNm	1.73E+04	2.02E+04	1.63E+04	17.06%	-5.92%
RootMzb2	B2 Root Mz	kNm	2.96E+02	3.71E+02	6.21E+02	25.38%	110.15%
RootMxb3	B3 Root Mx	kNm	1.83E+04	1.89E+04	1.83E+04	3.29%	-0.29%
RootMyb3	B3 Root My	kNm	1.73E+04	2.02E+04	1.64E+04	16.75%	-5.07%
RootMzb3	B3 Root Mz	kNm	2.96E+02	3.71E+02	6.24E+02	25.37%	111.18%
RootMxc1	B1 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.88E+04	1.97E+04	2.24E+04	4.97%	19.16%
RootMyc1	B1 Root My fix	kNm	1.60E+04	1.83E+04	3.71E+04	14.34%	131.32%
RootMzc1	B1 Root Mz fix	kNm	2.95E+02	3.69E+02	3.52E+04	25.21%	11834.48%
RootMxc2	B2 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.88E+04	1.97E+04	2.24E+04	5.00%	19.18%
RootMyc2	B2 Root My fix	kNm	1.60E+04	1.84E+04	3.71E+04	14.63%	131.07%
RootMzc2	B2 Root Mz fix	kNm	2.96E+02	3.71E+02	3.52E+04	25.39%	11798.99%
RootMxc3	B3 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.88E+04	1.97E+04	2.24E+04	5.04%	19.17%
RootMyc3	B3 Root My fix	kNm	1.61E+04	1.84E+04	3.71E+04	14.10%	129.94%
RootMzc3	B3 Root Mz fix	kNm	2.96E+02	3.71E+02	3.52E+04	25.37%	11804.60%
YawBrFxp	TT Fx	kN	5.79E+02	5.37E+02	6.86E+02	-7.12%	18.50%
YawBrFyp	TT Fy	kN	4.12E+02	5.75E+02	3.46E+02	39.56%	-16.01%
YawBrFzp	TT Fz	kN	1.00E+02	1.09E+02	1.13E+02	8.41%	12.15%
YawBrMxp	TT Mx	kN	1.68E+03	2.11E+03	1.81E+03	25.64%	7.64%
YawBrMyp	TT My	kN	7.49E+03	7.88E+03	8.04E+03	5.25%	7.44%
YawBrMzp	TT Mz	kN	6.86E+03	6.94E+03	7.16E+03	1.15%	4.34%
TwrBsFxt	TB Fx	kN	1.06E+03	8.28E+02	1.21E+03	-21.92%	14.32%
TwrBsFyt	TB Fy	kN	8.82E+02	1.01E+03	6.85E+02	14.24%	-22.38%
TwrBsFzt	TB Fz	kNm	1.63E+02	1.71E+02	1.95E+02	4.91%	19.95%
TwrBsMxt	TB Mx	kNm	6.49E+04	7.75E+04	5.07E+04	19.47%	-21.91%
TwrBsMyt	TB My	kNm	8.24E+04	6.77E+04	9.40E+04	-17.84%	14.08%
TwrBsMzt	TB Mz	kNm	6.80E+03	6.94E+03	7.09E+03	2.03%	4.23%
LSShftFxa	RotThrust	kN	3.52E+02	3.30E+02	3.57E+02	-6.42%	1.30%
FAIRTEN1	FAIRTEN1	kN	1.24E+02	1.36E+02	1.44E+02	9.43%	15.81%
FAIRTEN2	FAIRTEN2	kN	1.58E+02	1.72E+02	1.66E+02	9.05%	5.09%
FAIRTEN3	FAIRTEN3	kN	1.72E+02	1.78E+02	1.70E+02	3.62%	-1.04%

9.2.2 DELs grouped by wind speed (SOFTWIND)

A comparison of the chosen set of DELs, grouped per wind speed, is reported for the SOFTWIND model. The following figures report a comparison of the main statistical parameters, as previously defined, for the SOFTWIND model.

Blade root 1 Hz DELs grouped by wind speed are shown in Figure 64. DL underestimated edgewise DELs at 5 m/s mena wind speed due to differences in rotational speed. With respect to flapwise loads (BR My) OF tends to overestimate DELs respect to the other two codes at all wind speeds. IT must be noted that the load sensors shown in Figure 64 pitch with the blades for QB and OF but not for DL. Therefore, as blade pitch increases with increasing wind speed, we can expect differences to amplify.

Figure 64: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 1 root actions in blade reference system. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

PSDs of edgewise (BR Mx) and flapwise (BR My) blade root loads are shown in Figure 65 for various wind speeds during normal operation (DLC 1.2). Edgewise bending moment is dominated by response at the blade passing frequency (1P). OF and QB are similar in this regard, but peaks are lower for DL at this frequency. Flapwise loads on the other hand are also influenced by low frequency components. These are the frequencies that turbulent wind is most

likely to excite and where the controller is active. At 13 m/s (Figure 65 (e)) a strong peak in correspondence of the floater pitch natural frequency appears in the BR My PSD. At 23 m/s (Figure 65 (f)) mean wind speed response is again dominated by the blade passing frequency. Higher PSDs at the 1P frequency were also noted by some of the authors in a previous study, focused on onshore wind turbines [33], where they were attributed to differences in aerodynamic modelling. Particularly in differences in how non-uniform wind fields are treated.

Figure 65: Power spectral density plots for edgewise (BR Mx) and flapwise (BR My) blade 1 root bending moments for SOFTWIND test case in DLC1.2: (a,d) 7 m/s wind speed, (b,e) 13 m/s wind speed, (c,f) 23 m/s wind speed. All simulations in a wind speed bin are concatenated and PSD is calculated on entire bin.

Blade root 1 Hz DELs grouped by wind speed in the coned reference system are shown in Figure 66. Over estimation of flapwise and edgewise DELs for most windspeeds is noted for DL. This may be due to an issue with exporting data from this software but was not investigated in detail within the framework of the work package.

Figure 66: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 1 root actions in non-pitching reference system. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 67: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Tower base data. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Tower base 1 Hz DELs grouped by wind speed are shown in Figure 67. In most cases, good agreement is noted up to rated wind speed, where difference start to emerge and increase as wind speed increases. In particular, OF seems to underestimate fore-aft DELs (TB Fx, TB My), and DL underestimates side-side DELs, but to a lesser extent (TB Fy, TB Mx).

Figure 68: Power spectral density plots for side-side (TB Mx) and fore-aft (TB My) tower base bending moments for SOFTWIND test case in DLC1.2: (a,d) 7 m/s wind speed, (b,e) 13 m/s wind speed, (c,f) 23 m/s wind speed. All simulations in a wind speed bin are concatenated and PSD is calculated on entire bin. OF underprediction of TB My in wave frequency range discussed in section 9.2.2.

The reasons for the observed discrepancies are apparent upon perusal of Figure 68. The PSDs of the three codes agree well for TB Mx at 7 m/s mean wind speed (Figure 68 (a)). As wind speed increases, DL tend to predict less response in the wave frequency excitation band than QB and OF (Figure 68 (b, c)). On the other hand, in the fore-aft direction wave frequency response appears to be almost absent in OF, explaining the lower lifetime DELs that are noted for this code. Upon examining selected time series, it appears that first-order potential flow excitation forces are significantly lower in OF in the fore-aft direction. In the side-side direction, OF and QB agree well. Excitation forces were not exported for DL so we cannot verify their

magnitude relative to the other two codes. While the difference in the side-side direction for DL may be explained through different model tuning, as discussed in section 4.1.1, the reason for the apparent underestimation of excitation forces in the fore-aft direction for OF is currently unknown.

Figure 69: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Tower top data. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 70: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Shaft loadings. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 71: SOFTWIND spar floater Lifetime DELs. Mooring loads. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

9.3 COMPARISON OF DAMAGE EQUIVALENT LOADS FOR THE OC4 MODEL

9.3.1 Lifetime DELs comparison (OC4)

A comparison of the Lifetime DELs are reported for the OC4 model in this section. Good statistical convergence on blade root fatigue loads was reached as blade root DELs on the three blades are quite similar (Table 18). For this reason, only DELs relative to blade one are shown in Figure 72.

For this testcase OF tends to estimate higher DELs than QB. For blade root bending moments (M_x and M_y) this overestimation is in the range of 2-5%, while for tower loads the differences increases. For fore-aft quantities, which are the most influenced by aerodynamic loads, differences around 12% are noted (TT F_x , TB F_x , TB M_y). OF estimates higher tower DELs also in the side-side direction, but to a lesser extent, with discrepancies of around 9%.

Figure 72: OC4 spar floater Lifetime DELs. (left) Blade 1 root data in blade reference system. (right) Blade 1 root data in non-pitching reference system.

Figure 73: OC4 spar floater Lifetime DELs. Tower top data.

Table 18. Lifetime DELs for key load sensors for the OC4 model. Percentage difference of DL values respect to QB predictions in right column.

sensor	Label	Units	QB	OF	OF-QB diff. (%)
RootMxb1	B1 Root Mx	kNm	6.29E+03	6.42E+03	2.03%
RootMyb1	B1 Root My	kNm	6.51E+03	6.77E+03	4.08%
RootMzb1	B1 Root Mz	kNm	1.15E+02	9.99E+01	-12.77%
RootMxb2	B2 Root Mx	kNm	6.29E+03	6.42E+03	2.03%
RootMyb2	B2 Root My	kNm	6.53E+03	6.74E+03	3.22%
RootMzb2	B2 Root Mz	kNm	1.15E+02	9.98E+01	-12.89%
RootMxb3	B3 Root Mx	kNm	6.29E+03	6.42E+03	1.94%
RootMyb3	B3 Root My	kNm	6.48E+03	6.79E+03	4.85%
RootMzb3	B3 Root Mz	kNm	1.14E+02	9.98E+01	-12.67%
RootMxc1	B1 Root Mx fix	kNm	6.49E+03	6.70E+03	3.26%
RootMyc1	B1 Root My fix	kNm	6.01E+03	6.18E+03	2.87%
RootMzc1	B1 Root Mz fix	kNm	1.15E+02	9.99E+01	-12.77%
RootMxc2	B2 Root Mx fix	kNm	6.49E+03	6.70E+03	3.22%
RootMyc2	B2 Root My fix	kNm	6.03E+03	6.15E+03	1.94%
RootMzc2	B2 Root Mz fix	kNm	1.15E+02	9.98E+01	-12.89%
RootMxc3	B3 Root Mx fix	kNm	6.49E+03	6.69E+03	3.07%
RootMyc3	B3 Root My fix	kNm	6.00E+03	6.19E+03	3.17%
RootMzc3	B3 Root Mz fix	kNm	1.14E+02	9.98E+01	-12.67%
YawBrFxp	TT Fx	kN	2.09E+02	2.36E+02	12.75%
YawBrFyp	TT Fy	kN	1.18E+02	1.31E+02	10.75%
YawBrFzp	TT Fz	kN	6.80E+01	7.13E+01	4.82%
YawBrMxp	TT Mx	kN	6.74E+02	8.91E+02	32.14%
YawBrMyp	TT My	kN	2.82E+03	2.84E+03	0.57%
YawBrMzp	TT Mz	kN	2.89E+03	2.74E+03	-5.02%
TwrBsFxt	TB Fx	kN	2.59E+02	2.90E+02	12.04%
TwrBsFyt	TB Fy	kN	1.55E+02	1.69E+02	9.20%
TwrBsFzt	TB Fz	kNm	9.11E+01	9.31E+01	2.21%
TwrBsMxt	TB Mx	kNm	1.10E+04	1.20E+04	9.54%
TwrBsMyt	TB My	kNm	1.81E+04	2.03E+04	12.24%
TwrBsMzt	TB Mz	kNm	2.91E+03	2.74E+03	-5.83%
LSShftFxa	RotThrust	kN	1.27E+02	1.28E+02	0.52%
FAIRTEN1	FAIRTEN1	kN	4.43E+01	4.62E+01	4.28%
FAIRTEN2	FAIRTEN2	kN	1.53E+02	1.45E+02	-5.14%
FAIRTEN3	FAIRTEN3	kN	3.87E+01	4.06E+01	4.94%

Figure 74: OC4 spar floater Lifetime DELs. Tower base data.

Figure 75: OC4 spar floater Lifetime DELs. Mooring loads.

9.3.2 DELs grouped by wind speed (OC4)

A comparison of the chosen set of DELs is reported for the OC4 model. The following figures report a comparison of the main statistical parameters, as previously defined, for the OC4 model.

As shown in Figure 76, the relative difference between OF and QB DELs grouped by windspeed tends to increase as wind speed increases for edgewise bending moment (Mx) and to decrease for flapwise bending moment (My).

Further insight can be derived from observing Figure 77, where Power Spectral Densities (PSD) of blade root edgewise (a-c) and flapwise (d-e) bending moments are shown. At 7 m/s mean wind speed (Figure 77 (a,d)), the most energetic frequencies for edgewise bending moments are located around 1P. The frequency in Figure 77 is normalized by the mean revolution frequency for each wind speed and for each code. Therefore, as rotational speed is not constant, a larger spread in Figure 77 (a) indicates larger variations in rotor speed. Flapwise loads on the other hand (Figure 77 (d)) are mostly driven by low-frequency components. These low frequencies are mostly excited by the turbulent wind and by the apparent wind that low-frequency platform motions may cause. Response is larger for OF at these frequencies, as well as around 1P, although mostly insignificant at this mean wind speed.

Figure 76: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 1 root actions in blade ref. system. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

At higher wind speeds, BR Mx is dominated by 1P response, which is quite similar between the two codes (Figure 77 (b,c)). Flapwise bending moment now also shows strong response at the blade passing frequency ((Figure 77 (e,f)). At 13 m/s mean wind speed the controller is transitioning between below rated operation – where torque control is active – to above-rated operation – where blade pitch control is active. In this region, small differences in aerodynamic loads can trigger this transition and cause significant loading differences, as observed in [33].

The derated controller that is used in the current study, is active in the low frequency range, below 1P, where QB and OF behave quite similarly at this windspeed. The most significant differences are observed at blade passing frequency. Such differences are also noted in [33] and could be attributed to the different treatment of the non-homogeneous turbulent wind field between QB and OF. At 23 m/s average windspeed ((Figure 77 (f)), the most energetic signal components are again around 1P. A larger spread in frequencies can be noted for OF due to the increased variability in rotor speed respect to QB.

Figure 77: Power spectral density plots for edgewise (BR Mx) and flapwise (BR My) blade 1 root bending moments for OC4 test case in DLC1.2: (a,d) 7 m/s wind speed, (b,e) 13 m/s wind speed, (c,f) 23 m/s wind speed. All simulations in a wind speed bin are concatenated and PSD is calculated on entire bin

The near absence of low-frequency excitation in the PSDs can be attributed to the following factors; firstly, at high wind speeds relative speed variations are smaller than at lower wind ones, as defined by IEC standards [4]. Secondly, as blade pitch increases, loading shifts from the outer to the inner parts of the blades, decreasing the effect of load variations of bending moments. As observed by [33], 1P loads dominate the response, and they are mainly caused by the

inhomogeneities in the wind field. Differently from [33], however, QB and OF are found to be in good agreement, and consequently the difference in DELs (Figure 76) are found to be small. Interestingly, there is no apparent trace in the PSDs of blade root bending moments, of response at the wave excitation frequency (located approximately around half of the blade passing frequency for this test case). Finally, the PSDs in Figure 76 (e,f) suggest that wave induced motions do not contribute significantly to BR My loading for this testcase. This is in contrast with the SOFTWIND testcase, and also with the Hexafloat testcase, as discussed later on, where the effect of platform motion on the BR My PSD can be clearly seen. A possible explanation for the reduced amplitude of the PSD of BR My in the wave-frequency range is given by Goupee et al. [38]. In fact, the authors found that the unique characteristics of the OC4 semi-submersible yield a net zero motion of the nacelle at 90m above sea water level in intermediate sea states. This is due to the fact that surge and pitch response are out of phase and tend to compensate each-other. If the wave-induced motion of the rotor is small, the fluctuations in relative velocity on the blade at the wave frequencies will also be small, leading to the observed differences with respect to the SOFTWIND and Hexafloat testcase.

Blade root bending moments 1Hz DELs grouped by wind speed in the coned coordinate system – that does not pitch with blade – are shown in Figure 78. Very similar trends to 1Hz DELs in the blade reference system (Figure 76) can be noted, and the same considerations that were drawn for the latter hold true for the former.

Figure 78: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 1 root actions in blade non-pitching ref. system. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Very little variation was observed in both 1Hz and lifetime DELs among the three blades, indicating good statistical convergence of the results. Therefore, results for blades 2 and 3 are omitted and reported in appendix A.

Tower base 1Hz DELs grouped by windspeed for the OC4 testcase are shown in Figure 79. Although both codes agree well in general trends, the largest differences in both fore-aft (TB My) and side-side (TB Mx) DELs can be seen at 9 m/s mean wind speed. OF estimates higher DELs for both metrics. Upon examination of the PSDs of the tower base bending moments, excitation of the first tower fore-aft and side-side bending modes is noted in 9 m/s mean wind speed simulations. In fact, for this wind speed the 3P frequency is close to the first tower bending mode. As shown in Figure 80 (a, d), a larger peak in response near the 3P frequency is shown for OF in both fore-aft and side-side tower base bending moment. This is the first tower natural frequency. At higher wind speeds (Figure 80 (b, e)) tower bending modes move closer to 2P frequency and both OF and QB behave similarly, although some differences can be seen at 23 m/s mean wind speed in Figure 80 (c). The larger 1Hz DELs in TB My for OF at 23 m/s (Figure 79) seem to be caused by larger response at the floater pitch natural frequency and in the wave excitation band, although OF and QB behave overall quite similarly (Figure 80 (f)).

Figure 79: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Tower base data. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 80: Power spectral density plots for side-side (TB Mx) and fore-aft (TB My) tower base bending moments for OC4 test case in DLC1.2: (a,d) 7 m/s wind speed, (b,e) 13 m/s wind speed, (c,f) 23 m/s wind speed. All simulations in a wind speed bin are concatenated and PSD is calculated on entire bin

Figure 81: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Tower top data. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 82: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Shaft loadings. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 83: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Mooring loads. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

9.4 COMPARISON OF DAMAGE EQUIVALENT LOADS FOR THE HEXAFLOAT MODEL

9.4.1 Lifetime DELs comparison (HEXAFLOAT)

A comparison of the Lifetime DELs are reported for the HEXAFLOAT model in the following figures, for different sets of load components.

Lifetime DELs are generally lower for DL than they are for QB, as shown in Table 19. As discussed in section 5.5, not all the simulations runs could be completed for DL. Therefore, because some simulations are missing, we expect lifetime DELs to be lower for DL. Lower DELs are noted for blade root loads (Figure 84), Tower top loads (Figure 85), with the exception of yaw bearing bending moments, tower base loads (Figure 86) and tendon tensions (Figure 87). Tower top bending moments, particularly TT Mx differ greatly among the two codes. The larger lifetime DELs recorded for DL are in line with the larger standard deviations and peak values that are noted for this load sensor in Figure 25.

Figure 84: HEXAFLOAT spar floater Lifetime DELs. (left) Blade 1 root data in blade ref. system. (right) Blade 1 root data in blade non-pitching ref. system.

Table 19. Lifetime DELs for key load sensors for the Hexafloat model. Percentage difference of DL values respect to QB predictions in right column.

sensor	Label	Units	QB	DL	QB-DL diff. (%)
RootMxb1	B1 Root Mx	kNm	1.83E+04	1.80E+04	1.73%
RootMyb1	B1 Root My	kNm	1.64E+04	1.46E+04	12.98%
RootMzb1	B1 Root Mz	kNm	2.82E+02	6.51E+02	-56.63%
RootMxb2	B2 Root Mx	kNm	1.83E+04	1.80E+04	1.69%
RootMyb2	B2 Root My	kNm	1.64E+04	1.46E+04	12.64%
RootMzb2	B2 Root Mz	kNm	2.83E+02	7.74E+02	-63.44%
RootMxb3	B3 Root Mx	kNm	1.83E+04	1.80E+04	1.64%
RootMyb3	B3 Root My	kNm	1.64E+04	1.45E+04	13.22%
RootMzb3	B3 Root Mz	kNm	2.83E+02	1.03E+03	-72.61%
RootMxc1	B1 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.87E+04	2.37E+04	-21.01%
RootMyc1	B1 Root My fix	kNm	1.52E+04	3.78E+04	-59.81%
RootMzc1	B1 Root Mz fix	kNm	2.82E+02	3.47E+04	-99.19%
RootMxc2	B2 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.87E+04	2.37E+04	-21.02%
RootMyc2	B2 Root My fix	kNm	1.52E+04	3.78E+04	-59.78%
RootMzc2	B2 Root Mz fix	kNm	2.83E+02	3.47E+04	-99.18%
RootMxc3	B3 Root Mx fix	kNm	1.87E+04	2.37E+04	-21.01%
RootMyc3	B3 Root My fix	kNm	1.52E+04	3.78E+04	-59.80%
RootMzc3	B3 Root Mz fix	kNm	2.83E+02	3.47E+04	-99.18%
YawBrFxp	TT Fx	kN	6.20E+02	5.70E+02	8.84%
YawBrFyp	TT Fy	kN	6.46E+02	6.14E+02	5.23%
YawBrFzp	TT Fz	kN	1.20E+02	1.08E+02	10.90%
YawBrMxp	TT Mx	kN	2.15E+03	7.21E+03	-70.14%
YawBrMyp	TT My	kN	7.55E+03	9.89E+03	-23.61%
YawBrMzp	TT Mz	kN	6.83E+03	7.07E+03	-3.43%
TwrBsFxt	TB Fx	kN	8.63E+02	7.62E+02	13.28%
TwrBsFyt	TB Fy	kN	7.42E+02	6.91E+02	7.39%
TwrBsFzt	TB Fz	kNm	1.66E+02	1.51E+02	9.76%
TwrBsMxt	TB Mx	kNm	8.61E+04	7.70E+04	11.76%
TwrBsMyt	TB My	kNm	8.33E+04	7.17E+04	16.21%
TwrBsMzt	TB Mz	kNm	7.02E+03	7.20E+03	-2.48%
LSShftFxa	RotThrust	kN	3.38E+02	2.95E+02	14.50%
TendTens1	TendTens1	N	9.90E+05	9.14E+05	8.41%
TendTens2	TendTens2	N	1.02E+06	9.43E+05	8.65%
TendTens3	TendTens3	N	8.84E+05	8.23E+05	7.44%
TendTens4	TendTens4	N	9.69E+05	8.88E+05	9.09%
TendTens5	TendTens5	N	1.00E+06	9.21E+05	8.98%
TendTens6	TendTens6	N	8.96E+05	8.34E+05	7.43%

Figure 85: HEXAFLOAT spar floater Lifetime DELs. Tower top data.

Figure 86: HEXAFLOAT spar floater Lifetime DELs. Tower base data.

Figure 87: HEXAFLOAT spar floater Lifetime DELs. Mooring loads.

9.4.2 DELs grouped by wind speed (HEXAFLOAT)

A comparison of the chosen set of DELs is reported for the HEXAFLOAT model. The following figures report a comparison of the main statistical parameters, as previously defined, for the HEXAFLOAT model.

In Figure 88 the 1Hz DELs grouped by windspeed are shown for blade root bending moments in the blade reference system. Edgewise loads (RootMxb1) are higher for QB at low windspeeds and are fairly similar between the two codes at higher windspeeds, although some differences in IQR can be noted. Since edgewise loads are mainly caused by gravity, the differences at low wind speeds are caused by the different rotational speed in the two codes, as shown in Figure 23. Flapwise loads (RootMyb1) for DL are higher than QB at low wind speeds, equivalent around rated wind speed and lower above-rated. Flapwise loads (RootMzb1) for DL are higher than QB at low wind speeds, equivalent around rated wind speed and lower above-rated.

Figure 88: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 1 root actions in blade ref. system. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

PSDs of blade root edgewise and flapwise loads for the Hexafloat test case at various mean wind speeds are shown in Figure 89. Edgewise loads are dominated by 1P response (Figure 89 (a-c)). As for flapwise loads, at 7 m/s the PSDs for both codes are dominated by low-frequency

components (Figure 89 (d)). At 13 m/s (Figure 89 (e)), the response at the blade passing frequency is still much less pronounced than low-frequency response. Here, contrary to OC4, a peak in correspondence of the platform pitch frequency can be clearly observed, testifying the importance of the floater pitch motion on relative inflow velocity for this test case.

Figure 89: Power spectral density plots for edgewise (BR Mx) and flapwise (BR My) blade 1 root bending moments for Hexafloat test case in DLC 1.2: (a,d) 7 m/s wind speed, (b,e) 13 m/s wind speed, (c,f) 23 m/s wind speed. All simulations in a wind speed bin are concatenated and PSD is calculated on entire bin.

QB predicts a much larger response than that of DL at this frequency. At 23 m/s mean windspeed, low frequency response is still present, but it is much less relevant than 1P response. As seen for the SOFTWIND test case the 1P peak is much broader as for the DTU 10MW rotor rotation frequency is near the upper edge of the wave excitation range at this wind speed. In fact, at 23 m/s wind speeds, peak spectral periods between 8 and 14 s have been simulated in DLC 1.2. Similarly to the SOFTWIND test case, the influence of wave-induced platform motion on blade root edgewise loads can be observed.

Tower base DELs grouped by mean wind speed are shown in Figure 91. Tower base DELs are found to be in very good agreement not only in median value but also in IQR and in maximum and minimums. An exception to this are the fore-aft tower loads (TB Fx, TB My) near rated wind speed, where QB-predicted DELs are higher than DL-predicted ones. To separate sources of tower loading, PSDs of fore-aft and side-side tower base loads are shown in Figure 92 for selected windspeeds. In absence of significant aerodynamic damping, since a wind heading of 0° is used for all simulations in DLC 1.2, side-side tower base loads (Figure 92 (a-c)) are dominated by natural frequency response.

In fact, although the peaks in the PSDs in Figure 92 (a) and Figure 92 (b,c) appear at different relative frequencies, this is because they are normalized by different rotational frequencies, and the peaks are located at the same absolute frequencies. The lowest frequency peak is the system’s roll eigenfrequency, while the other is a tower side-side mode where the counterweight oscillates 180° out of phase with the structure. Fore-aft loads on the other hand are not as affected by this resonance, that is only somewhat apparent at 23 m/s mean wind speed (Figure 92 (f)) and is well captured by both codes.

Figure 90: HEXAFLOAT DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 1 root actions in blade non-pitching ref. system. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 91: HEXAFLOAT DELs grouped by wind speed. Tower base data. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Near rated wind speed (Figure 92 (e)), higher response at the floater pitch natural frequency for QB is highlighted. This is the cause of the higher 1HZ DELs that are apparent for QB in Figure 91.

Figure 92: Power spectral density plots for side-side (TB Mx) and fore-aft (TB My) tower base bending moments for Hexafloat test case in DLC 1.2: (a,d) 7 m/s wind speed, (b,e) 13 m/s wind speed, (c,f) 23 m/s wind speed. All simulations in a wind speed bin are concatenated and PSD is calculated on entire bin

Figure 93: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Tower top data. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 94: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Shaft loadings. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

Figure 95: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Mooring loads. The box extends from the lower to upper quartile values (boxes), medians (lines), whiskers (range of the data).

10 OBSERVATIONS

Good agreement between the codes can be generally observed for all the tested FOWT models. Some observations are reported in the following sections regarding the main outcomes of the comparative analysis.

10.1 SOFTWIND MODEL

10.1.1 Statistic data analysis

For the considered load sensors, the following statistical data have been considered:

- mean value (horizontal dash in previous plots);
- standard deviation (box in previous plots);
- maximum and minimum values (whiskers in previous plots).

Some considerations on the general statistical trends (related to normal operation DLC 1.2) as observed in the data are indicated below:

10.1.1.1 Average values

- Platform displacements are on average lower for QB than they are in DL and OF (Figure 5). This can be noted looking at Surge and Sway, and is also observable in Pitch and Roll. Differences in mean heave are attributed to the different buoyancy tuning and mooring line tuning in the three models, and carry over from previous work that was carried out within the project [2];
- OF generally provides relatively larger estimates for the blade pitch angle (Figure 6); the rotational speed predicted by DL is smaller, compared to OF and QB results, below the rated speed, especially at 5 m/s and 7 m/s where it appears as the minimum rotor speed of 6 rpm is not enforced in DL. In fact, in DL the minimum blade pitch schedule and the minimum rotor speed are not enforced by the ROSCO controller. This is due to a different implementation of the controller in DL. Similarly to QB and OF, in DL external control routines can be integrated through an external dynamic link library (.dll). For compatibility reasons however, the .dll was re-compiled for DL. We did not have the chance to investigate this further as for the current test case the difference only affects minimum rotor speed and thus is not relevant for wind speeds greater than 7 m/s. Above-rated, the results from the three codes for rpm average values match, complying with the control required value;
- Generator power is slightly larger for QB in comparison with the other codes (Figure 6);

- The mean value of the longitudinal force at the tower top and tower base for the SOFTWIND model (TB Fx in Figure 7) is relatively larger in for OF compared to QB results, at least up to the rated wind speed, while DL, on the other hand, yields a relatively lower value; the maximum average longitudinal force at the tower base, in particular, is observed around the rated wind speed, as expected for a pitch-controlled turbine, where QB estimates an intermediate value between the other two codes; the difference between the predictions of the three codes for the tower base force average value, which is anyway rather small, tends to reduce even further above-rated wind speed;
- A similar trend is also observed for the fore-aft bending moment at tower base (TB My in Figure 7);
- The above-mentioned differences may be related, at least partly, to the difference in the aerodynamic models applied within the codes. While OF and DL are based on a BEM aerodynamic model, QB relies on a lifting line free vortex wake aerodynamic model. In fact, the predicted aerodynamic thrust average value (Aero Thrust in Figure 9) is larger for OF, compared to QB, below rated speed, while this trend is reversed above-rated speed. A study on the comparison between different aerodynamic modelling approaches, reported in [1], showed relatively lower average values of rotor thrust for OF in comparison to QB, in an onshore application. In this floating case study, the load on tower top and tower base can also be influenced by gravitational loading due to the platform motion, which may justify the different behaviour with respect to the onshore case. Moreover, a clear trend cannot be indicated, as the two codes using a BEM-based approach (OF and DL) predict average values both above and below the lifting-line based code for TB My (Figure 7); only in the range of wind speed between 13 m/s and 17m/s both OF and DL overestimate the results from QB, but with very small differences;
- Similar trend as for TB Fx can be seen for the tower top longitudinal force TT Fx in Figure 8; QB sits between OF and DL for most mean wind speeds;
- The average value of tower top side-side moment (TT Mx in Figure 8) reaches a maximum around rated wind speed and remains constant for larger wind speeds. This is due to reaction forces to generator torque extraction;
- Regarding the aerodynamic thrust (Figure 9), the mean values predicted by OF are slightly larger below the rated wind speed and, conversely, smaller above-rated; the predicted values are rather close to each other despite the different aerodynamic models used by the two codes (LLFVW for QB and BEM for OF);

- Regarding blade deflection (Figure 10), the predictions by OF, QB and DL are in relatively good agreement, with OF predicting relatively smaller mean deflections and larger oscillations. DL tip deflections were only exported for the SOFTWIND test case in DLC 1.2. Therefore, ultima values of this sensor are not compared for DL, and the comparison is limited to the generally good agreement that can be noted in Figure 10;
- the average value of the blade root edgewise bending moment (BR Edgewise Mom. in Figure 10) show a sudden reduction around rated speed for OF and QB, which is not shown by DL;
- The BR flapwise moment is relatively larger for QB at higher wind speeds, while general good agreement with OF is noted below rated;

10.1.1.2 Range of oscillations

- For control related parameters (Figure 6), the generator power generally shows smaller oscillations in QB predictions, with larger oscillation predicted by OF below rated and larger predictions from DL above the rated wind speed; the pitch oscillations are generally relatively larger for QB from the rated wind speed to about 17 m/s, above this threshold DL predicts larger oscillations;
- The oscillation ranges (represented by the whiskers in the statistical comparison graphs) for the tower base loads are always lower in OF prediction for the longitudinal actions (TB Fx and TB My in Figure 7), while DL show the largest oscillations and QB exhibits an intermediate behaviour;
- The transverse tower base loads (TB Fy and TB Mx in Figure 7), on the opposite, are larger for OF, while QB still shows an intermediate behaviour between the other two codes. Such behaviour may be, to some extent, related to the effect of the platform motion, which exhibits larger oscillations in DL for the longitudinal motion (surge and pitch in Figure 5), while the transverse motion predictions (sway and roll) are slightly larger in range for OF; this trend, anyway, is less clearly observable particularly around rated wind speed;
- For tower top loads, OF generally predicts smaller ranges for the longitudinal force, TT Fx in Figure 8. On the other hand, for the transverse force, TT Fy in Figure 8, OF predicts larger ranges. A unique trend cannot be defined for the transverse moment, TT Mx, which shows larger oscillations below rated in OF predictions, while for large above-rated wind speeds OF predicts larger oscillations in TT Mx;

- With the exception of large wind speeds (larger than about 17 m/s), OF generally estimates larger oscillations for the blade root bending moments (Figure 10), particularly for the edgewise bending moment component. Above this wind speed the difference in oscillations between the codes tends to reduce. QB generally predicts ranges of oscillations with intermediate amplitude compared to the other two codes.

10.1.2 Maximum values

In terms of maximum loads the following observations are reported:

- With respect to platform motion (Figure 28), QB and OF are in good agreement in terms of the specific DLC in which the extreme value is found, but OF generally predicts larger peak displacements than QB. One exception to the agreement between OF and QB can be observed for the yaw peak value, for which OF predicts a significantly larger peak than QB. DL predictions often show peak values in different DLCs respect to OF and QB, and estimates larger peaks in surge, heave and pitch, while having lower peaks in the sway and roll DOFs;
- Blade root flapwise bending moments (B1 Root M_y in Figure 29) are in decent agreement. QB predictions are between OF (higher) and DL (lower). For all three codes and all three blade peak loads are located in DLC 1.6, indicating good statistical convergence of the calculations. Upon examination of Time series (Figure 30), it was noted how peak flapwise loads are related to large relative inflow differences due to platform motion. The different behaviour in DL can be explained in two ways; i) due to how boundary conditions are imposed, there is a time-shift in the inflow wind speed respect to OF and QB ii) there are differences in pitch controller actuation. Such differences could be caused by the time-shift in inflow, slightly different dynamics or by a slightly different ROSCO controller implementation, and would require further analysis to properly assess.
- Edgewise root bending moments are in good agreement for QB and DL, and peak loads are located in DLC 1.4 for both codes. Peaks for OF are located in DLC 6.3. As shown in Figure 31, in OF a large un-damped resonance at the first blade edgewise mode is apparent in DLC6.3 which causes the peak loading.
- Out-of-plane blade root bending moments (Figure 29) show the same trends discussed for flapwise bending moments. In-plane loads on the other hand are predicted during normal operation for OF and DL but in parked conditions for QB. All three codes are comparable in terms of magnitude of the ultimate loads;

- DL predictions with respect to blade deflections are significantly lower than the other two codes; upon examination of the dataset it was concluded that a different sensor was exported from DL, and thus, values are not comparable to OF and QB. Therefore, DL data was not included. Future analyses will try to further investigate this point by trying to export the right sensor and/or using different common exporting points for all the codes;
- Agreement in fore-aft tower base force (TB Fx in Figure 32) is very good. Similar good agreement is also noted for fore-aft bending moment (TB My) for QB and OF. A larger value is estimated in DL in parked conditions (DLC 6.1). Analysing time series in Figure 33, very good agreement in platform dynamics, which influence the tower base load significantly, can be seen in operating conditions (DLC 1.6), while large discrepancies are apparent in parked conditions for all three test cases (DLC6.1). This consideration was not strictly noted in the other test cases and the reasons are currently unknown.
- Larger spread in extreme values of side-side quantities is noted (TB Fy and TB Mx in Figure 32). Examining Time series, maximum bending moments are again very tightly related to platform motion. As shown in Figure 34, roll motion is lower for DL and consequently also is TB Mx.
- With respect to rotor thrust (Figure 36) QB and OF are again in good agreement;
- Control related maxima (Figure 37) show nice agreement between all the codes, with a relatively lower value of the generator torque predicted by DL;
- Also, the longitudinal forces predicted at the tower base (Figure 32) are very similar for all the codes, while at the tower top (Figure 38) DL predicts a higher peak in TT Fx. The agreement for the transverse load (TT Fy) is generally poorer.

10.1.3 Damage Equivalent Loads

Regarding the DELs post processing analysis, the following considerations are sketched below:

- For the blade root flapwise bending moments in the blade pitching reference system (B1 Root My in Figure 60), generally OF produces larger estimates (somewhat consistently with the larger estimates of the oscillation ranges from the statistical data); the prediction for the flapwise DEL (B1 Root My) is generally higher for DL. 1Hz DELs grouped by windspeed are shown in Figure 64. OF overestimates B1 Root My for all wind speeds. DL is in general in better agreement. Upon examination of PSDs in Figure 65, we can conclude that most of the differences are near 1P and at low frequencies. For B1 Root

My (Figure 64) instead the largest discrepancies are at below-rated wind speeds. As this load is typically driven by gravity, most of the energy is at blade passing frequency (Figure 65);

- Tower top DEL for the longitudinal force (TT Fx in Figure 61) shows significant differences among the codes, with larger values predicted by DL and QB in an intermediate position, as often observed in this comparison. For the transverse forces, the trend between the codes is reversed, with larger values predicted for OF and with QB halfway between the other codes. For the tower top moments, generally QB provides lower estimates of the DELs;
- Results for the tower base force DELs are similar to the tower top estimates (Figure 62), with QB in intermediate positions between the compared code results (except for the vertical force, where QB gives the lower estimate). If we examine the PSDs of tower base fore-aft and side-side bending moments in Figure 68, we can note how fatigue damage appears to be driven by hydrodynamics, as most of the energy in the signals is in the wave frequency range and in correspondence of the platform natural frequencies. OF appears to severely underestimate fore-aft excitation in correspondence of the wave frequencies. At the time of writing this is being investigated and the reasons are unclear;
- Regarding the mooring load DELs, similar results have been observed for the three compared codes, with no regular trend emerging.

Similar considerations as indicated above, can be reported also for the short time DELs as a function of wind speed, at least for the overall trend; anyway, it is difficult to directly relate the wind speed grouped results to the lifetime DEL estimate due to the fact that different bins have different numbers of simulations, according to the different probability of each wind speed interval. As a general trend, as noted previously, the difference in the results for the flapwise and pitching blade root moments, in the blade reference system, (as seen in Figure 64) tends to increase for larger wind speeds; while for the edgewise component larger difference can be noted at lower wind speed.

10.2 OC4 MODEL

For the OC4 model similar trends can be observed compared to the ones discussed for the SOFTWIND model. For this model only OF and QB data are available. Throughout this phase of the project, the OC4 QB and OF models have shown very good agreement. Among the three test cases it has been the easiest to calibrate and run smoothly. Therefore, overall differences are small, but nonetheless they will be summarized herein.

10.2.1 Statistic data analysis

Regarding the comparison of the overall statistic data the following observations are reported:

10.2.1.1 Mean values

- Larger mean values of the surge displacements (Figure 12) are predicted by OF for larger wind speeds.
- As noted for the SOFTWIND rotor, mean generator power is higher for QB below rated (Figure 13). On the other hand, at lower Tip Speed Ratios (TSRs), corresponding to higher mean wind speeds in Figure 13, a higher blade pitch can be noted for OF;
- Small differences between the two codes in terms of mean values can be observed; anyway, relatively larger mean values are predicted by QB for the tower base longitudinal force and moment (TB Fx and TB My in Figure 16), in contrast to what observed for the SOFTWIND model, suggesting that the differences between the models has no clearly identifiable trend, but may be depending on the model characteristics; the magnitude of the observed differences are anyway very small (and, particularly for TB My, tend to reduce at larger wind speeds);
- For large wind speed OF predicts relatively larger mean values of TT My;
- In this analysis also 2nd order hydrodynamic terms were included (in Figure 20 the 2nd order contribution to the horizontal hydrodynamic force is compared). Some differences may be noted, but the values of the 2nd order terms are an order of magnitude lower than the 1st order terms, that are in very good agreement;

10.2.1.2 Range of oscillations

- For platform oscillations (Figure 12), the ranges predicted by OF are generally larger than the predictions from QB;
- An abnormal oscillation range for wind speed around 17 m/s in TT Mx (Figure 15) can be observed. After examining the time series data it was determined that the maximum and minimum values occur in seed 213 and 193. In both cases the generator abruptly transitions from rated torque to a lower torque value in reaction to the combination of lower wind speed and rapidly increasing platform pitch caused by the instantaneous wave field, which lowers the relative inflow on the rotor even further. The step-change in torque appears to excite the first tower side-side mode in OF, leading to the observed peaks. QB appears to be less affected by the step-changes. It must be noted that this phenomenon is only apparent in the OC4 testcase because a minimum pitch saturation

as a function of wind speed is imposed in the ROSCO controller: once the minimum pitch is reached, the torque controller reduces torque to maintain rotor speed. Three main reasons for the difference in this regard can be identified: i) QB rotor speed varies less in both events, possibly because of the different aerodynamic model. This causes the step-change in torque to generally be smaller ii) Rotor speed is slightly different in QB and OF, leading to the step change in torque to occur in different time instants iii) QB is not affected by side-side resonance. This is most likely in virtue to the more accurate multi-body non-linear structural model that is employed;

- The oscillation ranges in tower base longitudinal bending moment (TB My in Figure 16) are comparable, while the ranges of the transverse moment (TB Mx in Figure 16) are larger for OF;

10.2.2 Maximum values

The excellent agreement that was noted in the statistical analysis in the previous section is also noted in extreme loads.

- Flapwise extreme loads are in very good agreement (Figure 40), with OF predicting a 1% higher load than QB. In this test case the critical load case is the one where the turbine is operating in extreme turbulence (DLC 1.3). The same good agreement is also noted for out-of-plane loads, although large outliers for OF can be noted. These are caused by a resonance issue recorded in DLC 6.2 where blade pitch is 90°. This issue will be commented on in detail when discussing edgewise loads. From the time-series analysis in Figure 41, the excellent agreement between QB and OF in DLC 1.3 can be confirmed. The only difference of note is regarding rotor speed, which is higher in QB due to the increased torque in these simulations. This ultimately leads to higher aerodynamic thrust.
- Edgewise loads for OF are some 80% higher than QB (Figure 40). As also noted for the SOFTWIND platform, such a difference is coming from edgewise instability at the blade natural frequency, shown in Figure 42.
- Fore-aft tower base extreme loads are very close. OF is 1.2% lower than QB in TB My and 0.4% lower in TB Fx. Time series in proximity of the extreme event are shown in Figure 44, in DLC1.6 at 23 m/s mean wind speed. At this high windspeed the difference in rotor speed and thrust disappears and instead a difference in mean blade pitch is apparent, as noted when discussing statistical values in DLC 1.2. Although extremes values are very close, higher excitation at the tower natural frequency in OF is apparent.

- Side-side loads do not agree as well as fore-aft tower base loads (Figure 43). From the analysis of the Time series in Figure 45, larger oscillations at the tower side-side natural frequency for QB can be seen. The higher side-side loads can therefore be attributed to the different structural models.
- Tower-top forces (Figure 48) are in excellent agreement

10.2.3 1 Hz Damage Equivalent Loads

Generally, OF predicts larger DEL values, except for the mooring loads, where the DEL estimates based on QB results are larger for the cable line tensions. In more detail:

- Flapwise blade root lifetime DELs are 3-4% higher for OF depending on the blade (Table 17). From the analysis of 1Hz DELs it is apparent how most of the overestimation comes from low windspeeds (Figure 76). Upon examination of PSDs (Figure 77), at low wind speed most of the differences are at low frequencies (wind excitation) and at the blade passing frequency. At higher wind speeds most of the excitation in BR My is at the blade passing frequency.
- For edgewise blade loads, similar considerations are valid. DELs are approximately 2% higher for QB (Table 17), and most of the energy in the signal is at 1P (Figure 77).
- Tower base loads are overestimated for OF to a greater extent. Fore-aft lower base bending moment (TB My) is overestimated by 12% while TB Mx of 9.5%. The increased tower base side-side bending moment is caused by increased energy at the first tower side-side bending mode frequency in OF (Figure 80).

10.3 HEXAFLOAT

The dynamics of the HEXAFLOAT model are very different from the ones of the previous two floaters. In general, this can be attributed to two reasons; firstly, the mooring lines were designed without any specific constraint on platform displacement during operation. This resulted in a lightweight catenary system that allows for large displacements of the system. This contributes in part to the fact that platform pitch and roll natural frequencies are also very low. Secondly this is a two-piece floating structure made of slender bodies, as opposed to the previous one-piece structures with relatively low Keulegan-Carpenter number. For this model only DL and QB data are available.

10.3.1 Statistic data analysis

With respect to the statistical data analysis, the following observations can be reported:

- Platform surge (Figure 21) is relatively larger in QB predictions for wind speeds lower than the rated speed, while for larger wind speeds DL predicts larger mean values; a similar trend is observed for the platform pitch angle;
- Rotational speed mean values (Figure 23) as predicted by DL are smaller for below rated wind speeds. This trend is consistent with what was observed in SOFTWIND simulations;
- Blade pitch mean values (Figure 23) are smaller from DL, particularly immediately after the rated wind speeds;
- Tower base longitudinal force and moment mean values (Figure 24) from DL results are larger for below rated wind speeds, and lower at higher wind speeds compared to QB results; this trend is similar to the one observed for platform pitch and surge, suggesting that these loads, as expected, are significantly influenced by platform motion;
- A similar inversion in the mean levels of the predictions by QB and DL can be seen for the tendon loads (Figure 27).

10.3.2 Maximum values

Regarding the maximum values the following observations can be reported:

- Platform maxima are in good agreement with respect to the values, but sometimes the maximum is predicted in different DLC;
- Blade root flapwise and out-of-plane extremes are approximately 9% lower of DL. At the same time edgewise loads are up to 20% higher for DL (Figure 51). The difference is less significant for in-plane loads (Figure 51).
- Tower base extreme loads generally agree very well, one exception is TB M_x (Figure 54).
- Time series are not as closely matched than in the previous test cases, where DL and QB could be compared, because of the noticeable shift in wind speed that is apparent in Figure 52, Figure 53, Figure 55 and Figure 56. This being said, the two codes agree relatively well during normal operation, while sometimes large differences are noted in parked conditions. This is being investigated at the time of writing and is somewhat surprising, since during previous phases of the project [2], the most disagreement between the codes was noted when aerodynamic loads were introduced.
- The other compared maxima are generally in good agreement.

10.3.3 Damage Equivalent Loads

Regarding DELs, blade root moment estimates by QB show larger values. Tower base loads, also, as predicted by QB are higher, while shaft loads and tower top moment DELs are higher from DL estimates. Tendon loads are generally higher in the predictions by QB.

11 CONCLUSIONS

An extensive code-to-code comparison of FOWT simulation codes has been presented in this work. Three codes are compared; QB which was extended and developed within the FLOATECH project, OF, a state-of-the-art open-source tool, and DL, a commercial code that is used in industry. More than 750 simulations are performed for each code and for each of the three test cases that have been selected. Met-ocean conditions representative of an offshore site west of the Scottish isle of Barra have been used. The three test cases were simulated in parked and in power production conditions, in a variety of sea-states. The effect of wind speed, significant wave height and peak spectral period on the offshore structure's performance and loads have all been considered. An effort was made to use identical wind speed and wave height inputs in all three codes. This effort was mostly successful, with the exception of a time shift in the turbulent wind fields in DL, which we were unable to remove.

The three test cases, the NREL 5MW on the OC4 semi-submersible platform, the DTU 1MW on the SOFTWIND spar platform and the DTU 10MW on the HEXAFLOAT floating platform, have all shown particular traits. For instance, blade root bending moments in the OC4 test cases look quite similar to an onshore turbine: peak flapwise loads are found in extreme turbulent inflow (DLC 1.3) and fatigue loads are mainly driven by wind excitation and 1P response. On the other hand, for the SOFTWIND platform, DLC 1.6 with extreme waves was often the DLC where the highest loads were recorded. Large variations in platform pitch angle have been noted in severe seas, that coupled with the structure's low center of gravity and high tower, have resulted in large platform-induced rotor motions and velocities, with negative values of aerodynamic thrust being recorded at times. Finally, the Hexafloat platform is a two-part floater that has shown significantly different dynamics to the other two test cases once again. In particular the lightweight mooring system means that large displacements of the platform are allowed. Moreover, the system's natural frequencies are particularly low, with the platform pitch natural period being around 50 s.

When analysing the statistics during normal operation that are computed for the SOFTWIND model, generally good agreement in mean values is found, which testifies the good level of agreement that we were able to reach with the three independent set-ups. As for peak values, QB generally sits between OF, and DL. This trend carries over to extreme loads. Flapwise blade

root loads are 2-4% higher than QB for OF and 10-14% lower for DL. In this case extreme loads are recorded in DLC1.6 at high wind speeds, where the extreme waves cause large platform motions and thus large variations in relative velocity on the blades. Analysing Time series OF and QB appear to behave very similarly. In DL, different blade pitch activity is noted, possibly as a consequence of the different wind field. Edgewise loads are overestimated for OF, due to an edgewise blade resonance in parked conditions. On the other hand DL and QB agree well, and predict peak loads in DLC1.4. A delay in the blade pitch to feather procedure is noted in DL, which could explain the difference in extreme loads. As for tower base loads, hydrodynamic induced platform motions appear to influence design loads significantly. Tower base loads are slightly smaller for OF (-3% and -4% in side-side and fore-aft bending moment respectively), but up to +/- 25% differences for DL can be seen. This is attributed to the different model tuning approach that was followed for this test case in DL, which could lead to different dynamics when the turbine is parked in severe sea conditions, as observed in this work.

Blade-root Lifetime DELs are higher in both the edgewise (3%) and flapwise (17%) directions for OF. Flapwise lifetime DEL for DL on the other hand is lower than QB (-5%). From a spectral analysis, at low windspeeds there are differences at very low frequencies, possibly indicating a different treatment of the incoming flow turbulence. Around rated wind speed the influence of platform motion on flapwise loads is apparent. The cause of this excitation at the platform natural frequency is still under investigation but it is likely not only caused by hydrodynamic loads as it is not apparent at higher wind speeds. Moreover, no second-order potential flow loads are considered in QB, that shows the highest response in flapwise load. At high wind speeds, most of the differences are near the 1P frequency. As for tower base loads, significant differences between the codes have emerged in the wave excitation frequency band, which appears to be a main contributor to the fore-aft and side-side tower base bending moment signal energy especially at high wind speeds. In particular OF underestimates the fore-aft excitation severely. Thus, tower base bending moment lifetime DEL results are somewhat uncertain.

For the OC4 test cases, generally higher torque and rotor speed below rated for QB, that uses a LLFVW model are noted. Extreme blade root loads in the flapwise direction are 2% to 4% lower for OF. Tower base extreme fore-aft loads show a similar trend and are between 0.5% and 1.2% lower for OF. Fatigue loads on the other hand are higher for OF. While the discrepancy is limited for blade root loads, where lifetime DELs are approximately 4% higher, tower base fore-aft and side-side bending moments are 12% and 9.5% higher respectively. As for the reasons that lead to these differences, it was found that, due to the higher torque that is predicted in QB, rotor speed and thus thrust forces are slightly higher than OF when the controller is transitioning from below to above-rated wind speed. As the TSR is higher so is rotor

thrust; a possible explanation for the higher flapwise loads. Edgewise blade root loads and side-side tower loads are in less good agreement. It is found that edgewise blade root loads for OF are affected by an undamped resonance when the turbine is parked and the blades are feathered. This resonance is not apparent in QB, where a multi-bod explicit FEA model is used to compute blade deformations. Side-side tower base loads also appear to be influenced by the structural modelling differences. In fact, peak loads occur in parked conditions, and they are higher for QB as a consequence of oscillations around the tower natural frequency that are apparent when examining the signal, and are stronger for QB than OF.

As for fatigue loads, spectral analysis has revealed how these loads differ the most at low wind speeds, where low-frequency, wind-driven excitation differences emerge. At higher wind speeds the blade passing frequency (1P) also becomes relevant for fatigue flapwise loads as a consequence of wind shear and turbulence, but overall QB and OF agree well, and no clear trend can be noted. Tower base loads are once again influenced by the structural modelling, in particular the side-side loads. In OF, the tower base natural frequency is excited, leading to the difference that was noted in the lifetime DELs.

In the Hexafloat test case, the relative QB-DL trend that was observed for the SOFTWIND platform is confirmed. Flapwise design loads are 11% lower and edgewise loads are 1.5% lower approximately for DL. Upon examination of Time series it appears as generally, during operation, QB and DL agree well. A shift in the response of the two machines is often noted due to the shift in incoming wind field as seen by DL. Near rated wind speed, different controller actuation is noted, which may explain part of the difference in peak loading. Tower base extreme loads are similar in the fore-aft direction but less so in the side-side direction, where the differences in tower and platform dynamics are more apparent in the presence of complex excitation and absence of aerodynamic damping.

Fatigue loads are generally lower for DL for this test case. The same considerations that were reported for the SOFTWIND model appear to hold true here too. As for the SOFTWIND testcase, not all simulations in DLC 1.2 could be completed in DL (section 5.5). The impact of this was not evaluated but it will probably result in slightly lower DELs. The number of incomplete simulations is small and the probability of occurrence of the incomplete simulations is low, reducing the impact on lifetime DELs. Lower lifetime DELs for blade root flapwise moments appear to be caused by lower 1P response in high wind speeds and lower response at the platform pitch natural frequency near rated wind speed. As for side-side loads, the tower's natural frequency stands out in both QB and DL. In the fore-aft direction loading appears to be more complex with waves and low-frequency platform motions also playing a role.

In summary, considering the information that is presented for all three test cases the following can be concluded:

- General trends and statistics are similar for all three codes. Extreme loads and fatigue loads are similar comparing one blade to another in all three test cases, indicating that good statistical convergence of simulations is reached
- Overall better agreement between QB and OF is noted than between QB and DL. This can be caused by i) different tuning of hydrodynamics for SOFTWIND test case ii) shift in the incoming turbulent wind field with respect to QB and OF iii) different controller actuation in DLC1.4, when blades are feathered to shut turbine down iv) differences in ROSCO controller implementation (rotor speed below rated and absence of pitch saturation). Control actions, particularly blade pitch actuation, appear to be significantly different in DL than they are in the other two codes.
- Flapwise blade root extreme loads for OF and QB are comparable (+/- 4% depending on test case). For DL, lower flapwise peak loads are recorded (-10/-14%). Larger differences in edgewise loads due to edgewise instability that was seen in OF. Edgewise peak loads are found in DLC 1.4 for QB and DL. The different blade pitch actuation in DL may be the cause of the differences.
- Tower base extreme loads (bending moments) are also comparable of OF and QB. OF is found to be approximately 0.5%-4% lower than QB in these metrics depending on specific load and test case. These loads are mostly influenced by hydrodynamics. On the other hand, large difference are noted for DL in the SOFTWIND test case (+/- 25%), likely due to the different model tuning. In the Hexafloat test case fore-aft loads are similar for QB and DL but not side-side loads. This is attributed to the complex loading and lack of aerodynamic damping, but needs to be investigated further.
- Fatigue loads are higher both at blade root and at tower base for OF. This is attributed to a mix of causes: differences in turbulent wind field treatment and sheared inflow treatment cause differences in aerodynamic loads at 1P frequency, difference in structural model cause larger tower mode excitation, especially for OC4. DL on the other hand, generally predicts lower fatigue loads. Contrary to OF, generally smaller excitation at 1P is noted in flapwise blade-root bending moments in DL. Although this code is not open-source, and not all the details of the specific BEM implementation can be known, the treatment of the non-uniform wind field should be quite similar to OF. A possible explanation of the differences could come from the treatment of non-aligned inflow and

the lack of tower shadow and dynamic stall modelling, but further investigation is needed to confirm this hypothesis.

- In parked conditions, larger differences between the three models are noted. These are partly due to instabilities in OF, where large undamped tower or blade excitation was noted in some simulations.

From a more general perspective, the following considerations are finally proposed. QB includes advanced numerical models for aerodynamics, which can be solved using LLFVW and structural dynamics, which are modelled with 1D non-linear multi body FEA. In particular, the possibility of properly solving the wake is seen as a major plus for future analyses of wind farm layouts (e.g., to further develop the active wake mixing techniques in WP4). It also includes a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that simplifies and significantly speeds-up the set-up process of complex simulations such as the ones performed herein. QB also includes pre-processing tools that can be used for blade design and airfoil aerodynamic coefficient computation and manipulation. The GUI also allows for fast post-processing and data visualisation, which is often not a feature of open-source tools. Despite the increased fidelity models, GPU acceleration allows the simulations to be run with a computational cost that is comparable to that of OF and DL, namely in the current study QB was found to have a computational cost that is in between those of OF and DL. QB has also proven to be robust: we were able to complete all the simulations in the database, something that was not possible within the framework of this work package with DL and OF due to the various numerical instability issues discussed in this report.

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13 APPENDIX A – ADDITIONAL 1HZ DELS

13.1 SOFTWIND

Figure 96: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 2 root actions in blade reference system.

Figure 97: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 2 root actions in non-pitching reference system.

Figure 98: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 3 root actions in blade reference system.

Figure 99: SOFTWIND spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 3 root actions in non-pitching reference

13.2 OC4

Figure 100: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 2 root actions in blade ref. system.

Figure 101: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 2 root actions in blade non-pitching ref. system.

Figure 102: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 3 root actions in blade ref. system.

Figure 103: OC4 spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 3 root actions in blade non-pitching ref. system.

13.3 HEXAFLOAT

Figure 104: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 2 root actions in blade ref. system.

Figure 105: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 2 root actions in blade non-pitching ref. system.

Figure 106: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 3 root actions in blade ref. system.

Figure 107: HEXAFLOAT spar floater DELs grouped by wind speed. Blade 3 root actions in blade non-pitching ref. system.